

**LIVING WITH UNCERTAINTY: PRESENCE OF ANTICIPATORY GRIEF
AMONG FILIPINO FAMILY CAREGIVERS OF MAJOR
NEUROCOGNITIVE DISORDER PATIENTS**

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Living with Uncertainty: Presence of Anticipatory Grief among Filipino Family Caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder Patients

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Abstract

Caring for a loved one with a Major Neurocognitive Disorder can be compared to a long train journey with no fixed route and no estimated time of arrival. This condition, formerly known as "dementia," is a progressive and incurable neurological disorder that impairs a person's cognitive and physical abilities. As a result, patients who had been diagnosed were left with caregivers who had the duty of caring for them. Prior studies have shown that family caregivers of patients with major neurocognitive disorders experience anticipatory grief, a stage of pre-death mourning brought on by manifestations of the disorder's impact on the patient. In the Philippines, Major Neurocognitive Disorder is not recognized as a significant public health concern that calls for an investment in medical research, causing the caregiver community to suffer and be labeled as the second invisible patient due to a lack of approved local guidelines (Agapito et al., 2018). It limits the possibility of conducting local studies on caregivers' experiences of anticipatory grief. This provided sufficient justification for the researchers to conduct a qualitative phenomenological study focusing on the family caregivers of patients with major neurocognitive disorders to determine the essence of a phenomenon of "uncertainty" through their lived experiences. Following Collaizi's methodological approach, the researchers created a self-made open-ended interview questionnaire. A total of ten selected respondents were interviewed using maximum variation sampling. The findings indicate that anticipatory grief is commonly experienced by family caregivers who have a patient with a severe major neurocognitive disorder, as it includes the disorder's worst symptoms, such as memory and functionality deterioration. The respondents reported anticipatory grief as a result of "uncertainty" caused by a lack of knowledge, resources, and support, resulting in self-doubts and a sense of helplessness. Indeed, there is uncertainty in anticipatory grief as a result of inadequate country policies for home-based family caregivers.

Keywords: *anticipatory grief, family caregivers, major neurocognitive disorder, uncertainty*

Introduction

"It is a strange, sad irony that so often, in the territory of a disease that robs an individual of memory, caregivers are often forgotten."

-Karen Wilder

Aging is an inevitable part of life. In the Philippine Statistic Authority (PSA) reported in 2020, Filipinos aged 60 and up comprised 8.5% of the population, or 9.2 million senior citizens. Moreover, 24.4% or 5,606,500 of the 22,975,630 households nationwide had at least one older member of the family (Philippine News Agency, 2022). The Philippines being a dominantly religious country, there are traditions that place a strong cultural value on respect for age and for the elderly. "Pagmamano", saying "po" and "opo" is a gesture that embodies the richly embedded Filipino culture that serves as a sign of respect and love for elders. We cannot deny that it is rooted firmly in Filipino society that the idea of caring for older people is the responsibility of their family. In a Filipino core value system, "Utang na Loob" refers to the concept of an obligation to appropriately repay someone who has done a favor, which is impossible to quantify due to the deeply personal and internal dimensions involved (Manalo et al., 2022). This Filipino psychological concept of repaying favors to elders who played a significant role in their lives is the reason why Filipino family members provide care. Unfortunately, in some cases, there are certain old persons who have a disease that leads to a progressive decline in cognitive functionality that makes them forget everything, including their family.

This disease was always associated with the concept of "nag-uuliyamin" or "makakalimutin," but truth is it must not be characterized as that because the condition has a deeper impact on both the patient and caregiver that must be recognized and addressed. This condition is known as Major Neurocognitive Disorder, and it is currently recognized as a progressive terminal illness with significant healthcare needs. According to the population commission, 490,000 Filipinos suffered from neurocognitive disorder in 2014-2015 (GMA public affairs, 2019). Besides, more than 55 million people worldwide suffer from this terminal illness, with nearly 10 million new cases diagnosed each year (WHO, 2022). Contrary to popular belief among many Filipinos, the neurocognitive disorder is not a natural part of aging (Reyes, 2017).

Patients with this disorder suffer from a mental illness that encompasses declination in memory, reasoning, and other cognitive functions (Sousa et al, 2020). In severe cases, the manifested symptoms include an inability to attend to one's own needs, a total loss of words resulting in ineffective communication, and a reversion to childlike behavior (Han, 2022). As a consequence of the advanced stage people with this condition will eventually die, and they are also at risk of dying from another illness that includes a neurocognitive disorder as a comorbidity (Nunns, 2015). As of now, it is the 7th leading cause of mortality globally (Webster, 2021). As a matter of

fact, unlike other life-threatening diseases, this condition appears to be unobtrusive during the initial stage because it typically begins with forgetting minor details until it becomes suddenly worse that results in death.

As a result of the distinct phases of this disorder, the diagnosed individual constantly requires full-time assistance from others, which is typically provided by family members who serve as the patient's primary caregivers. In fact, caring for a patient with cognitive disorder is much more difficult than caring for someone with another terminal illness like cancer or HIV. In a study by Jacobsen (2021), the sudden transition from living a normal life to becoming a neurocognitive disorder caregiver causes health, social, and psychological concerns. In addition, family caregivers are also at high risk of acquiring stress, anxiety, and depression due to various triggering sorts of situations and this often impacts their caregiving experience (Cheng, 2017).

To gain a deeper understanding of this phenomenon, the researcher will assess the lived experience of Filipino family caregivers of neurocognitive disorders at the end of life. Since the study of anticipatory grieving situations has received little attention, this research will serve to unravel the unspoken truth about this kind of scenario. In addition, some early research indicates that preemptive processing of a loss can help a person cope better once the loss occurs. Within this paradigm, the family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients are able to deal with any unfinished business, say their good-byes, clear any misunderstandings, and prepare for future social adjustments, resulting in a less distressing and disabling period of bereavement when death does occur (Forbes health, 2022). On the other hand, some family caregivers reported feeling relieved when their loved ones with neurocognitive disorder died (Lewis, 2015). They are ashamed to admit that they sometimes wish for the death of their loved ones with this kind of disorder out of a sense of burden and exhaustion. Indeed, as patients' progressive memory loss worsens, sometimes the embedded culture of respect for elders deteriorates.

It is still now a compelling issue that we need to talk about, there has been little research about this kind of phenomenon that we might one day experience. This kind of situation has no social strata; you could be the next person to experience caring for loved ones with Major Neurocognitive Disorder, or it could be one of your relatives, your mother, your father, your husband, or anyone in your family. The dearth in the literature raises the need for research incorporating the voices of primary caregivers to fully comprehend the complexities of advanced terminal dementia faced by families.

There are now a number of nursing homes in the country, but many Filipinos still don't consider to confine their loved ones in a care facility. It has been practiced by Filipinos to take care of the elder in a home care setting. Aside from that, the financial situation is another reason why a patient is not admitted to the hospital for an extended period of time. In the study of Borja (2021), there are currently no privileges given to the dementia caregivers regardless of their socioeconomic situation. Yet, the total cost of dementia care is PHP 849.2 million, of which PHP 321.3 million is spent on informal care. Given that the Philippines is a low-income country, this clearly shows the prevalence of burden.

Aside from the benefits that they received from the government, neurocognitive patients and their family caregivers are after the quality of life. In the world of continuous changes and fast discovery in the medical field, there is still no current national system of public healthcare that can give all the elements required to address this reality experienced by primary caregivers and their care recipients (ADAP, 2022). There is no legal case registry in the Philippines for neurocognitive disorders and related illnesses, indicating that we are not yet prepared to deal with this kind of situation. Dementia care is indirectly covered in the Philippines by Republic Act 9994; the 20% discount and VAT exemption is not enough to cover the needs of neurocognitive disorder patients and their carer (Zoleta, 2022). Especially for out-patients who do not have PhilHealth and cannot afford a monthly contribution during their younger years. As a result, this study is critical in assessing the lived experience of Filipino family caregivers to understand the essence of the phenomenon to better understand and enable the researcher to explore for solutions.

This study sheds light on an overlooked health concern in the Philippines, specifically people suffering from Major Neurocognitive Disorders and its caregivers. In this paper, the focal point is not on the Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients but rather on their family caregivers, who are regarded as the hidden patients of the illness. It is the shocking reality that there is a limited to lacking amount of support system among Filipino caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients as well as unheard cases of anticipatory grief piqued the researchers' interest.

Filipino family caregivers have been identified to be in an uncertain situation because the care recipients have a Major Neurocognitive Disorder that could cause their incremental loss of memory and sudden death. This is the reason why caregivers experience anticipatory grief while caring for a patient in a home setting. Care providers are unsure of when the death will occur, but they are certain that it could happen at any time. The basic and primary purpose of this phenomenological study is to reduce the individual experiences with a phenomenon with a description of universal essence.

Considering the qualitative nature of this study, a Phenomenological approach is an excellent choice for the research design, which will describe the lived experiences of several Filipino family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders. The researchers focus on describing what and how the participants have in common as they experience the said phenomenon.

The researchers will collect data by conducting semi-structured conversations with participants who have experienced this phenomenon. This data will then be subjected to Collaizi's methodological analysis, which includes becoming familiarized with the content by reading all of the participants' responses several times, extracting significant statements that are relevant to the phenomenon

being studied, and identifying meanings significant to the phenomenon that are grounded in careful deliberation. These identified meanings will be grouped into themes that are related to one another. Following that, the researchers will provide an in-depth description of the phenomenon using the generated themes. This comprehensive description will be condensed into a short statement capturing those aspects deemed essential, and the developed fundamental structure will be returned to the participants to ascertain whether it obtains their experience or not. If in case of inadequacy, modification of the earlier steps will be done.

Research Questions

The study aims to deliver an intensive description to the phenomenon of uncertainty being experienced by Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients. Results shall raise public engagement in relation to the concept of anticipatory grief, as well as stimulate national policies solely designed for Filipino family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders. The following research questions have been formulated in order to accomplish the study's objectives:

1. What are the lived experiences of Filipino family caregivers as they encounter anticipatory grief while providing care for patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders?
2. What is the essence of the anticipatory grief by Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients?

Methodology

Research Design

The purpose of this study was to understand the lived experience of family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive patients. To gain a complex understanding of the aforementioned issues qualitative research was conducted, as it was appropriate for the nature of this investigation into the experience. Researchers are inclined to learn more about how people make sense of their experiences in this approach (Merriam, 2009). It intends to gain an in-depth understanding of social phenomena in their natural setting, their home.

Determining the correct methodological approach for any research was critical to achieving the desired results. Hence, this research will use a descriptive phenomenological method to gather information that explains how individuals experience the phenomenon of uncertainty through looking at the lens of anticipatory grief in providing care for patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder. It describes the common meaning of several individuals' lived experiences of a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2012). It was conceptualized as a qualitative research approach to reveal the "essence" or "essential structure" of the participants' "lived experiences" and the meaning of their experiences (Colaizzi, 1978). This investigates the developing explanation of social phenomena without attempting to manipulate the situation in any way, other than to understand and interpret the data.

As the procedure progressed, the researchers formulated research questions to facilitate a deeper understanding of the phenomenon emphasizing the depth of caregiver anticipatory grief.

Participants

The participants included in the study are Filipino citizens living anywhere in the Philippines. Due to the difficulty of studying the entire population, researchers collected information from a drawn sample using a non-probability sampling method. Family caregivers of diagnosed Major Neurocognitive patients will be chosen using the maximum variation sampling technique. In this method, it is possible for researchers to intentionally pick individuals with varying caregiving experiences in order to represent a variety of perspectives without engaging with or collecting a large number of individuals (WHO, 2016). This is one of the most frequently used purposeful sampling designs because it enables the depiction of the world's complexity through the diverse views of individuals (Creswell, 2002).

Family caregivers are defined as individuals who provide regular care or assistance to a family member with a health condition or disability. They provide uncompensated material or emotional support and are typically family members (Quinn et. al, 2019).

In total, 10 participants were interviewed with the use of open-ended interview questions. Researchers asked questions until it reached the data saturation; i.e., the point at which no new data were obtained and the information gathered confirmed the previously gathered points. Accordingly, the qualified participants in the study are family caregivers;

Someone who is part of the family (e.g., spouse, siblings, uncles, aunt, cousins, nephews, nieces, and children)

A family caregiver with whom the care recipient engages in a more personal relationship and who offers a wide range of assistance.

Care providers who are at least 18 years old and have been providing care to the patient for at least a year. Family caregivers who live along with the care recipient in a home setting.

Instrument

Data collection instruments also pertain to devices such as questionnaires, tests, interviews, and surveys (Seaman, 1991). A small number of participants will be interviewed for this study's qualitative methodology using the following self-made questions that the researchers have prepared. As one of the main goals of this study is to better understand the phenomenon of uncertainty through the

lived experiences of Filipino family caregivers with Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients, the study's questionnaires are open-ended and consist of ten items, with desired responses aligned with the participants' actual experiences. In order to address the aforementioned research aims, the researchers have created these questions, which were examined and validated by a qualified expert prior to the data collection.

Procedure

To fulfill the study's motive, the subsequent procedures were observed and performed as a means to gather information from the samples. The researchers adhered to the protocols provided by the institution with regard to data collection; which pertains to passing the standards of research ethics to proceed with the study. This would imply that the documents required to be presented to the selected participants will be processed first including the validation of the questionnaire by a tool validator as well as the consent form to be discussed before the interview.

The primary instrument of the research is open-ended interview questions, that allow participants to respond in their own terms instead of offering a predetermined range of possible answers. This permits the researchers to investigate deeper into their participants' responses if they are not satisfied with the gathered data from structured questions, thereby researchers have the option to ask follow-up questions. Given that the participants in this study were selected via online platforms, the interview will be conducted based on their preferences, which may include phone calls, Facebook Messenger, Viber or Google Meet.

So as to achieve a successful interview, the researchers provided a set of guidelines to follow during the meeting:

The participants were accommodated one at a time for better communication and understanding between the researcher's prepared questions and the participant's responses.

The researchers introduced the topic to the participant and let them read and prepare themselves by giving the interview questions beforehand.

Throughout the interview, the researchers respected each participant by abiding the rights of research respondents.

The researcher treats the interview with confidentiality as stated in the consent form.

During the interview the researchers used an audio recorder in order to record the conversation with permission, especially the participant's answers

These procedures were done for every participant.

Data Analysis

As the structure of this study adheres to a qualitative approach, no statistical treatment was performed. Hence, this paper is more concerned with gathering the respondents' experiences to anticipatory grieving towards caregiving. As determined by Colaizzi (1978), a qualitative method provides the reliability and credibility of its conclusions as it is comprehensive and effective. It enables researchers to identify emerging themes and their interconnected relationships. Given that the researcher in this study will be responsible for studying the participants' natural environment of being a caregiver, the researchers suggest that the phenomenological approach is appropriate. Phenomenology as a methodological framework has evolved into a process that seeks reality in individuals' narratives of their lived experiences of phenomena (Cilesiz, 2009; Husserl, 1970; Moustakas, 1994). The general purpose of the phenomenological study is to understand and describe a specific phenomenon in- depth and reach at the essence of participants' lived experience of the phenomenon. (Cilesiz, 2010) Researchers utilizing the descriptive phenomenological approach consider this method as a clear and logical process for investigating the fundamental structure of a phenomena.

To illustrate the flow of generating the study's analysis, in order to interpret subjective experience and acquire insights into the participants' experiences, it will be interpreted using Colaizzi's process of phenomenological data analysis, which consists of seven distinctive step processes of analysis.

The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (Sanders, 2003; Speziale & Carpenter, 2007).

Familiarization - Researchers read each transcription several times in order to obtain a general sense about the whole content.

Identifying Significant Themes - Researchers extracted each transcription with identified significant statements that provide direct relevance to the phenomenon understudy the statements must be recorded on a separate sheet noting their pages and lines numbers.

Formulating Meanings - Researchers defined meanings formulated from significant statements. Each underlying meaning was coded in brackets or categories.

Clustering Themes - The researchers sorted the formulated meanings into categories that reflect a unique structure of clusters of themes. Each cluster of themes was coded to include all formulated meanings related to that group of meanings.

Developing and Exhaustive Description - The findings of the study were integrated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon

under study. The researchers wrote a full and inclusive description of the phenomenon, incorporating all the themes produced to form a distinctive construct of theme.

Producing the fundamental structure - The researchers condensed the exhaustive description down to a short, dense statement that captures just relevant aspects deemed to be essential fundamental structure of the phenomenon.

Seeking verification of the fundamental structure - The researchers validated the study’s findings through “member checking” technique to compare the researcher's descriptive results with the experiences sought from the research participants. Participants' views on the study results were obtained directly via phone calls. This step was done by the researchers that took the approval from the participants in advance during the initial interview. Eventually, all participants showed their satisfaction toward these results which entirely reflect their feelings and experiences.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Frequency & Percentage Distribution of the Respondents

Demographic Profile		Frequency	Percentage %
Age	20-35	1	10%
	36-40	2	20%
	41-45	3	30%
	46-50	4	40%
	Total	10	100%
Gender	Female	7	70%
	Male	3	30%
	Total	10	100%
Civil Status	Single	3	30%
	Married	5	50%
	Separated	1	10%
	Widowed	1	10%
	Total	10	100%
Occupation	Employed	6	60%
	Non-Employed	4	40%
	Total	10	100%
Relationship with the Patient	Parents	5	50%
	Grandparents	2	20%
	Siblings	1	10%
	Relatives	2	20%
	Total	10	100%

The frequency distribution in the table depicts the demographic profile of the respondents. It illustrates that Filipino family caregivers aged 40 to 60 make up the largest proportion of the population. 70% are females, with the remaining 30% being males. While some are single, the majority of these caregivers are married. Only 10% are separated or widowed. Furthermore, 60% of caregivers are employed, while the remaining 40% are unemployed. Finally, it has shown that the caregivers' relationship with their patients falls into the category of parents, which accounts for 50% of the population, 20% for grandparents and other relatives, and only 10% for siblings.

Colaizzi’s Methodological Data Analysis

The phenomenological approach has roots in the disciplines of philosophy and psychology. In this study, the researchers used Husserl's descriptive phenomenology and Colaizzi's method of analysis (1978). This methodological analysis introduces seven procedural steps, which include synthesizing each transcription's sense, extracting its key statements, constructing and clustering its meanings until it generates emergent themes.

Table 2. Emergent Theme: The Caregiver’s Relationship with the Patient

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	"bata pa lang ako sobrang attached na ako sa kanya since she spoiled me with love talaga" (Participant 1, Transcript A, Line 4-5).	Presence of attachment between the caregiver and the patient.
2	"Yung parents ko po kasi is OFW, kaya siya na po nagpalaki sa akin" (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 3-4).	Caregiver needs were met first by the patient before the diagnosis.
3	"Typical na family lang, nakabukod na kasi kaming lahat since we have our own families na pero every weekend nabisita kami sa parents namin and ayun, bonding, kainan" (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 3-4).	Prior to the diagnosis, the caregiver and patient were not living together.
4	"Sa totoo lang talaga, lumaki akong hindi gaano malapit sa tatay" (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 3).	Caregiving does not necessitate a close relationship with the patient.

5	"Si tita yung tumuring sa akin na parang tunay anak na rin niya. " (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 5-6).	The caregiver felt a sense of belonging because of the patient.
6	"Pagkatapos ng diagnosis, I was able to sense a disappointment sa kanya since during that time hindi pa naman siya ganoon ka-worst." (Participant 6, Transcript F Line 4-6).	After the diagnosis, the patient suffers from disappointment upon learning the condition of the disorder.
7	"nakaramdam ako ng mas malalim na involvement sa mga nangyayari sa kanya sa araw-araw." (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 4-5).	The caregiver gained a sense of responsibility and carefully observes the patient's everyday activities.
8	"Growing up I was fairly close with my grandfather, binibisita namin siya every time may chance kami mostly every vacation but since he was diagnosed" (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 3-6).	Presence of attachment between the patient and caregiver that grew stronger due to the condition
9	"Sa totoo lang po right away ko siya parang natanggap kahit alam ko mabigat yung situation namin kasi alam ko kailangan ko magkaroon ng strong personality" (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 9-11).	Presence of attachment between the patient and caregiver that grew stronger due to the condition.
10	"Honestly feel ko I developed my purpose of becoming her daughter." (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 5-6).	Respondent grew closer to the patient and found a sense of purpose.

Participant 1. The presence of attachment between the caregiver and the patient has been observed since the caregiver's childhood. This would imply that the Participant 1 is appreciative to the patient, as the patient has provided care to the Participant 1 since childhood.

Participant 2. Caregiver needs were met first by the patient prior to the diagnosis since the parents of Participant 2 are working abroad and the patient has decided to stand in the role of Participant 2's parents since childhood.

Participant 3. Prior to the diagnosis, Participant 3 and the patient were not living together, so they were not that close.

Participant 4. According to Participant 4, Participant 4 did not grow up close to the patient. Although the caregiver and patient relationship are frequently tense and complicated. This would mean that close relationship with the patient is not required for caregiving.

Participant 5. Participant 5 has felt a sense of belonging since childhood. This would indicate that Participant 5 has core relationships with people who genuinely care about them.

Participant 6. According to Participant 6 that prior to the diagnosis, the intimacy between the caregiver-patient was well received. Closer relationships between caregivers and patient with MND are associated with better outcomes for the patient.

Participant 7. The caregiver developed a sense of duty following the patient's MND diagnosis and carefully observes the patient's everyday activities. A caregiver is just a duty or a helper for non-medical activities as they offer consistent and dependable company.

Participant 8. There's existence of a deep emotional bond between the patient and Participant as a result of their illness. The relationship between the patient and participant 8 can still be deep and fulfilling even though the patient's cognitive decline makes it possible for them to no longer be able to share the same level of emotional or physical intimacy that they previously did.

Participant 9. Participant 9 is motivated to care for the patients out of a sense of duty and reciprocity. Intrinsically motivated caregivers may be less likely than extrinsically motivated caregivers to experience caregiver burden as a result of insufficient reciprocity (Reid, Moss, & Hyman, 2007).

Participant 10. For participant 10, the satisfaction of knowing that the patient they loved is receiving exceptional treatment because of the care he provided increased meaning and purpose in his life, aside from giving back to someone who had cared for them.

Table 3. Emergent Theme: Acceptance of the Caregiver in Patients Conditions

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	"it took me months before ko matanggap yung adjustments na mangyayari sa buhay ko and ang nagiging motivation ko lang talaga is yung love ko sa mother ko" (Participant 1, Transcript A, Line 15-17).	Months of adjustments guided by love for the patient.
2	"hindi ko na po namalayan kasi ang naging mindset ko ay alagaan lang lola" (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 8).	For young caregivers, the mindset is light and simple.
3	"kasi during the first part parang sumasabay lang ako sa agos ng mga ginagawa or need gawin" (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 10-11).	The respondent is simply going with the flow until the patient's disorder becomes apparent.
4	"matagal talaga bago ako naka-adjust or nakasabay sa changes kasi hindi pala biro yung sakit na ganito lalo na uncontrollable talaga yung possibilities eh. Mas naging determined ako sa trabaho" (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 9-11).	Internship programs aim to immerse students in the field of their profession.
5	"Sa pagiging caregiver, sobrang bilis lang kasi nung oras na malaman ko na may sakit siya nag step-up na talaga ako na ako yung mag-aalaga sa kanya""nung una hirap ako	There is a presence of initiative on the caregiver's side.

6	kasi akala ko wala lang yung sakit niya." (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 9-10). "Matagal-tagal rin eh kasi I was placed in a situation na naging curious ako sa mga bagay-bagay na related doon sa sakit niya. Inalam ko if through genetics ba, sa food na kinakain, sa lifestyle ba, lahat" "hindi ako comfortable sa sudden changes" (Participant 6, Transcript F Line 9-13).	Curiosity on the part of the respondent caused them to accept the circumstance and uncomfortable with sudden changes.
7	"Parang hindi ako dumaan sa processing ng thoughts kung ready na ba ako, tanggap ko ba" "may mga sudden outbursts ako ng emotions kapag nahihirapan ako sa pag-aalaga kasi hindi naman ako dumaan sa ganoon " (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 8-11).	Inability to absorb the situation, automatically jumps as the caregiver of the patient and sudden outbursts due to the difficulty in caregiving.
8	"it took me personally a year to finally adjust to it as it is still difficult for us to accept na yung condition niya will continuously worsen but still I want to make his healthier state worthwhile" (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 10-13).	A year to completely adjust prompted by the desire to spend longer valuable time with patient.
9	"Sa totoo lang po right away ko siya parang natanggap kahit alam ko mabigat yung situation namin kasi alam ko kailangan ko magkaroon ng strong personality" (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 9-11).	Respondent were inclined to embrace their condition immediately to become braver for the patient.
10	"It took some time but as for me, I was eager to learn about her condition. I want to understand our whole situation" (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 11-12).	The respondent's urge to learn the nature of the illness motivated her to accept reality.

Participant 1. According to Participant 1, accepting the change to being a caregiver requires months of modifications driven by love for the patient. This implies that coming to terms with the diagnosis requires time.

Participant 2. Taking care of someone who has a health problem is never simple; caregiver may be required to carry out ever-more-complex medical treatments. But, Participant 2 has a light and simple attitude as one of the greatest honors is to take care of those who have taken care of us in the past.

Participant 3. For some of the caregivers find it difficult to "go with the flow," but Participant 3 just follows the flow until the patient's problem is apparent and accepting that there are no cures for this progressive disease, and that the caregiver has no control over situations and events, releasing feelings of stress, relaxing a bit, and simply going with the flow.

Participant 4. Participant 4 had a long-term adjustment to new tasks, responsibilities, and duties as the disease progressed, which led him to play a more active part at work.

Participant 5. Lack of caregiver choice for Participant 5 resulted him to experienced emotional stress, physical strain and negative health effects at first.

Participant 6. Curiosity about the diseases leads Participant 6 to accept the situation, but as the disease progresses, the sudden changes make him uncomfortable.

Participant 7. For Participant 7 helping the patient who was in need and feeling that they could no longer fulfill their past duties caused a sense of role loss because of instantly takes on the position as the patient's caregiver, which resulted to the inability to process the situation, and exhibits unexpected outbursts as a result of the challenges of providing care.

Participant 8. According to Participant 8, taking time to digest the diagnosis is a critical first step in adjusting to and acknowledging the diagnosis. This compelled him to accept the patient's condition for more than a year, but he chose to disregard the extended period of acceptance because he desired to spend quality time with the patient.

Participant 9. Participant 9 was inclined to embrace the patient's condition right away because they were able of bottled up their emotions and were brave.

Participant 10. The desire to understand the nature of the illness is a significant predictor of participant 10 to the patient, which becomes her motivation to provide care and acknowledge reality.

Table 4. *Examples of Emergent Theme: Accumulated Daily Concerns of Caregivers towards the Disorder*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
3	"Pinipilit ko makahanap ng solusyon kahti sinabing incurable siya and yung memory loss is inevitable" (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 17)	Adapting and Learning the Nature of MND
10	"daily thoughts consist of continuous learning and adapting to the changes that I experience taking care of my mother" (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 19-20)	
1	"pero naapektuhan ako through being afraid of her death." "Yung way of living ng family ko is nagbago kasi from minding our own naging center na ng attention naming yung pag aalaga kay mama"(Participant 1 Transcript A Line 34-35)	Fear of patient's death
2	"Dalawa po iniinda ko noon, yung pagiging mag-isa pati po yung sakit ni lola" (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 19)	Sense of loneliness and helplessness.

2	"May mga araw po noon na wala akong maayos na tulog kaya lagi po akong nahuhuli sa pagpasok" (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 23-24)	Difficulty in time management and organization of priorities
5	"Non-stop yung mga thoughts na what if i-try ko ito, yan, yun, kasi desperate talaga ako na mapagalang siya. Umabot pa sa nakakapasa na ako ng late sa work outputs" (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 14-15)	
7	"Iniisip ko rin na hanggang saan kakayanin ng my own family yung situation namin sa bahay kasi pati talaga sila affected." (Participant 7, Transcript G Line 16-18)	
9	"Nasubukan talaga yung pagiging anak saka pagiging ina ko at the same time. I had to juggle my tasks. Naging kumbaga 50/50 ako sa parehas kong responsibilidad " (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 24-25)	Collective Emotional and Physical Stress
3	"Na-stress talaga ako ng malala and iba siya when it comes to burden"(Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 23)	
8	"the most noticeable effect it had sa family namin is yung emotional saka physical na stress talaga" (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 23-25)	
4	"May mga times na tumitingin ako ng mga facilities na nag-aalaga sa mga tulad niya. I considered na to send him sa mga ganoo" (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 19-20)	Consideration for Nursing Homes and MND community support groups
6	"naghanap hanap ako ng community groups or support para magkaroon naman ng idea kung paano ihahandle yung patient" "magmula noon hindi na ako masyado nag ooverthink" (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 16-18)	Caregiver constantly worries on the financial strain.
9	"iniisip ko na lang kung paano namin kakayanin yung pang-araw-araw na challenges ng pag-aalaga gawa na nga ng mayroon na din akong sariling pamilya. "(Participant 9, Transcript I, Line 19-20)	
8	"it was hard for us to adjust financially. Lagi ko iniisip yung time na to admit him to professional healthcare providers para maavail din yung PhilHealth assistance" (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 24-26)	
1	"Kaya naman naging daily thoughts ko na yung possibilities na lumala yung sa mother ko and makulangan ako ng resources" (Participant 1 Transcript A Line 27)	

According to Participant 1, their regular concern has been the symptoms and the resources needed to caring for a family member. Participant 3 is concerned with understanding disease treatment plans and medications. Within that particular reference, Participant 10 expressed the same issues. This would indicate that caregivers are having difficulties adapting to and learning about the nature of Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Participant 1 has always been dealing with the terror of the patient's untimely death throughout the time the disorder was recognized. Participant 2 was troubled by feelings of isolation and helplessness.

Participant 2, Participant 5, and Participant 7 are apprehensive about time problems and changes in direction of priorities. Participants indicate that the daily struggles with time management, managing obligations, and surrendering work performance in service of care giving are their daily concerns. Sleep deprivation has also been identified according to Participant 2

Participant 8 shows concern further about family's collective emotional and physical stress. Family caregivers are constantly anxious about the obligation as shared by Participant 3.

Participant 4 stated their everyday considerations of potentially admitting the relative to a nursing home when caregiving becomes challenging. Participant 6 expressed the same regular issue of seeking supports and guidance from the local community for Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

For Participant 9, realizing the nature of the disorder, continuously give her worry on everyday circumstances of becoming a caregiver. As shared by Participant 4 the situation makes him sad every day.

Participant 8 stated that financial stress affects her on a daily basis beyond the challenge of physical and emotional challenges. The financial strain of professional healthcare services and assistance worries them every day.

Table 5. Examples of Emergent Theme: Concept of Becoming a Caregiver and its Considerations

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	"greatest form of love" (Participant 1 Transcript A Line 41)	Personal Choice: Caregiving is a form of love
4	"Ito yung tinatawag na unconditional love kasi wala akong hininging kapalit from him, hindi ko nagawang magsumbat at magalit." (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 29)	
9	"pagiging caregiver is a devotion of your love" (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 29).	
6	"It serves as a true meaning of a family, yung hindi mag iiwanan hanggang tumanda at mamatay man " "kasi ang pagiging family caregiver ay bukal dapat sa loob."	

	(Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 21-23)	
1	"Syempre personal choice ko siya kasi mother ko yun eh, handa ako magpaka-kahit na ano para sa nanay" (Participant 1 Transcript A Line 44-45)	
4	"Personal choice ko siya kasi in the first place, tatay ko eh" (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 25)	
9	"personal kong choice ito kasi since mahal ko parents ko" (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 33).	
2	"From the word "family" talagang gagawin po ang lahat para po sa pamilya" (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 27).	
9	"Sa totoo lang po right away ko siya parang natanggap kahit alam ko mabigat yung situation namin kasi alam ko kailangan ko magkaroon ng strong personality" (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 9-11).	
2	"From the word "family" talagang gagawin po ang lahat para po sa pamilya" (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 27).	
5	"It's another way of saying "mahal kita, aalagaan kita" yung pagiging family caregiver is also a self-sacrifice kasi mas pipiliin mo na iwanan yung mga nakasanayan mo at sumakay sa changes na mangyayari during caregiving" (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 19-21)	MND leads family members to become immediate caregivers through Kinship and Connection
2	"Hindi ko naman po pinili noon na maging ganyan pero dahil nagkasakit po lola ko at ako lang kasama niya, matic po na nauwi na rin sa ganyan" (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 31-33)	
7	"Yung pagiging family caregiver ko is a life changer talaga, babaguhin talaga niya lahat and it is something na wala naman akong magagawa" "ako lang nag iisa niyang anak, matanda na rin si mama para alagaan siya" (Participant 7, Transcript G Line 21-23)	
8	"it really comes with great responsibility" (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 39)	Caregiving is more than the concept of Utang na Loob
10	"Being a caregiver for me is definitely a big responsibility brought about by love" (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 32).	
3	"To be a family caregiver is more than the thought of "utang na loob." (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 27)	Personal decision due to capabilities and availability
3	"nakikita ko rin naman talaga na mas may kakayahan ako para maalagaan at masuportahan sila" (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 32-33)	
8	"Yes, it's a personal choice. When our family discussed it parang considering everyone's lifestyle ako yung pinakacapable in terms of time availability and personal responsibilities" (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 43-44)	

Participant 1 believes that being a family caregiver is the greatest form of love. According to Participant 9, caregiving conveys unconditional love without reciprocity, as expressed consequently by Participant 4. Participant 2 described the concept of caregiving as the real definition of a family. To become a caregiver, it must be rooted from the heart and must be a willing decision

According to Participant 1, the decision to take on the role of caregiver is a personal commitment premised on the relationship with the patient. Participant 4 also indicated it was a personal choice because of familial kinship.

Participant 9 considers being the caregiver a personal choice prompted by love and connection for relative. Participant 2 is family oriented and expressed the same concept of the role.

Participant 2, in contrary expressed that caregiving in their case as not a personal choice but more of an act of service prompted by commitment to the relative. Participant 2 stressed that the disorder, Major Neurocognitive Disorder leads family members to become immediate caregivers. As defined by Participant 7, Family caregiver is a life changer as it transforms everything into a new situation and concludes that the disorder leads the respondent to become the family caregiver.

Participant 10 conveyed that the role of being the family caregiver is a personal choice to give back to the patient. According to Participant 3 it is beyond a sense of obligation

Participant 2, in contrary expressed that caregiving in their case as not a personal choice but more of an act of service prompted by commitment to the relative.

Participant 3 stated that being the caregiver was a personal choice because of their capability and availability to provide care for the patient. Participant 8, in consideration to other relatives, rather than a personal choice decided to take on the role as well upon family mutual agreement.

Participant 8 believes that being the family caregiver is a sense of responsibility. Participant 10 on the other hand thinks it is both a responsibility and the cause of love.

Table 6. *Examples of Emergent Theme: Filipino Family Caregivers' Emotional Outcomes as the Disorder Advances to Severity Phase*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	"Sobrang frustrating siya kasi hindi siya compared ng ibang sakit na nakukuha sa gamot, sa therapy, sa technology" (Participant 1, Transcript A Line 53-54)	The respondent is frustrated with the symptoms and lack of a treatment plan for the disorder.
2	"Sa ngayon po kasi malala na po lola ko, talagang kailangan na po niyang assistance sa lahat ng gagawin niya" (Participant 2, Transcript B Line 36-37)	The worst condition of MND calls for monitored assistance.
3	"Actually, sa tuwing naisip ko yan is kinakabahan ako kasi may doubt ako kung kakayanin ko ba or hindi" (Participant 3, Transcript C Line 37-38)	The respondent experiences self-doubt once the patient becomes dysfunctional.
4	"Natatakot ako for my family knowing na pwedeng umabot yung tatay ko sa sitwasyon sa iyon" "Personal choice ko siya kasi in the first place, tatay ko eh" (Participant 4, Transcript D Line 39-40)	Fear for their own family because of the awareness of the disorder's expected symptoms.
5	I feel like wala ng katapusan to and sobrang depressing niya. (Participant 5, Transcript E Line 30-31)	
6	"He will be needing a strict monitoring since ito yung stage na completely clueless na siya sa reality" "yung idea na mawala siya, parang I can compare it to a puzzle, may mawawalang piece na nung puzzle and never na mabubuo yung image" (Participant 6, Transcript F Line 26-28)	Strict monitoring as the patient becomes clueless about reality.
7	"Maaaring hindi na talaga siya mag respond sa lahat ng bagay at kinakatakot ko yun kasi pwedeng ako hindi niya ma-recognize bigla niyang masaktan ay ewan ko di ko na mahahandle yung emotion ko kapag ganon" "nakakapanlumo lang na hindi na siya makakaalala at wala na rin akong pwede pang magawa, ayun na yun eh" (Participant 7, Transcript G Line 26-27)	Failure to respond to the environment and the presence of the threat that the patient could hurt anybody.
8	"After learning that this specific condition has no cure really makes me lose hope" (Participant 8, Transcript H Line 48)	Respondent feels helpless as there is not enough support for outpatients of the disorder
9	"Sobra po akong malulungkot kasi itong stage pa lang po ni nanay na nalaman ko naiyak na po ako" (Participant 9, Transcript I Line 40)	The respondent is anticipated to grief
10	"I will probably feel anxious and break down" (Participant 10, Transcript J Line 40)	The respondent is anticipating being anxious

Frustration of being caregiver

Frustration can be difficult to manage when caring for a patient with Major Neurocognitive Disorder as shared by Participant 1 who is frustrated with the symptoms and lack of a treatment plan for the disorder. Every caregiver may experience moments of anxiety and frustration, but Major Neurocognitive Disorder, not the individual, can exacerbate these feelings in those who have never experienced it before.

Fear of progression

Fears about the disease's progression and the difficulties in providing future care, as expressed by Participant 10, can result in overwhelming tasks that prevent the caregiver from focusing on the present. As the patient's condition worsens, the caregiver's anxiety may increase, causing the participant to break down in tears. This is similar to Participant 4, but apart from that he's aware that the condition will get worse.

Caregiver dealing with helplessness

When considering the extensive caring journey that lies ahead, some caregivers expressed feelings of helplessness. Participant 8 feels vulnerable because there is insufficient support for disorder outpatients because this caregiver appears to lack the expertise and abilities needed. Being vulnerable as a caregiver presents an intriguing dilemma. This made it imperative to maintain composure, stand tall, and be strong when speaking out for their loved ones, giving the patients the impression that they have their backs, and never letting their vulnerability or anxiety show.

Caregiver suffering from self-doubt

Some caregivers try to make everything ideal and make impossible goals, but they eventually end up having self-doubt because they are unfamiliar with the disorder. This experience is comparable to the one experienced by Participant 3, who has had the same sentiments when the patient's conditions worsen and become dysfunctional. Maybe they could want to ensure that their patient is well-fed, comfortable, and clean. But being truthful to reality as the patient's symptoms worsen requires a different approach.

Caregiver Fatigue

Participant 5 stated that they were going through an endlessly depressing stage of life, as caring for a person with Major Neurocognitive

Disorder was like a thief who stole their previous, healthy, and joyful life, whereas Participant 7 mentioned that they were unable to manage their emotion, which manifested itself in angry outbursts towards the patient.

Table 7. *Examples of Emergent Theme: Personal Concern of Filipino Family Caregiver with the Patient*

<i>Participant No.</i>	<i>Specific Statement</i>	<i>Formulated Meaning</i>
1	"siguro yung idea na pwede siya makasakit unconsciously" (Participant 1, Transcript A Line 64-65)	Presence of Anxiety and Agitation on Patients
7	"Maaaring hindi na talaga siya mag respond sa lahat ng bagay at kinakatakot ko yun kasi pwedeng ako hindi niya ma-recognize bigla niyang masaktan" (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 26-27)	
2	"lagi na po ako nag ooverthink na baka makalabas po siya ng bahay at hindi na matandaan paano umuwi" (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 48-49)	
9	"Yung time talaga. Super hirap imanage. Kumbaga hindi namin hawak yung kinabukasan parang ganon." (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 55-57)	The feeling of uncertainty and incapability of proving care.
8	"Talagang appektado personal life and time ko. I don't mean it in a bad way ha" (Participant 8 Transcript H Line 65-68)	
5	"It is lack of cooperation by the patient that concerns me. Although I want to make her time worthwhile, it still depends to my mother's attitude for certain times which make me a little stressed out." (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 51-53)	The lack of cooperation of the patient.
3	"Lack of resources from the government both local and national" (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 46)	The lack of personal support for the Family caregiver.
5	"Yung suporta, nakukulangan ako sa pakiramdam na suportado ako" (Participant 5 Transcript E Line 30)	
6	"Financial matters talaga yung concern ko" (Participant 6 Transcript F Line 32)	Financial Struggle
4	"Hindi ko alam kung hanggang saan ko siya kayang maalagaan, what if kung magkulang pera ko, what if kung walang wala na talaga" (Participant 4 Transcript D Line 48-49)	

Presence of Anxiety and Agitation on Patients

Family caregivers of MND patients may fear that their loved ones could become aggressive or agitated, potentially leading to harm to themselves or others, due to the cognitive decline and behavioral changes associated with the disease. As shared by Participant 1, this fear is often fueled by the unpredictable and sometimes violent nature of dementia-related symptoms, which can make it challenging for caregivers to manage and provide care for their loved ones. This is similar to the statement of Participant 7. These indicate that this fear is rooted in the unpredictability of the disease, which can cause patients to exhibit erratic or aggressive behavior.

The feeling of uncertainty and incapability of proving care.

According to Participant 2 and Participant 9 they all experienced the feeling of uncertainty in the situation they are in. Family caregivers of dementia patients often feel uncertain about how to provide care because the disease can be unpredictable and symptoms can vary widely from person to person. Additionally, the emotional toll of watching a loved one decline can make it difficult for caregivers to know what the best course of action is. Finally, the physical demands of caring for someone with dementia can be overwhelming, especially as the patient's condition worsens over time.

The lack of cooperation of the patient

Based on the experience of Participant 8 and Participant 5, Family caregivers of dementia patients can have a difficult time with their loved ones in terms of cooperation due to the nature of the disease. Patients with dementia may become confused, disoriented, or agitated, and this can make it challenging for caregivers to communicate with them effectively. Additionally, patients may forget or resist help with tasks of daily living, which can cause frustration for caregivers. The decline in cognitive function can also make it difficult for patients to understand why certain tasks are necessary, leading to further resistance. Overall, caregivers may struggle to balance the needs and safety of their loved ones with their own mental and physical well-being.

The lack of personal support for the Family caregiver

According to Participant 3 and Participant 5, Family caregivers of dementia patients may have a hard time providing personal support to their loved ones due to the physical and emotional toll of the disease. Patients with dementia may require assistance with activities of daily living such as bathing, dressing, and eating, which can be physically demanding for caregivers. Additionally, patients may exhibit behavioral symptoms such as aggression or wandering, which can be emotionally challenging for caregivers to manage. Finally, caregivers may struggle to balance their own needs for rest and self-care with the demands of caring for a loved one with dementia.

Financial Struggle

It is evident in the statement of Participant 6 and 4 that financial problems can be a significant issue for family caregivers of dementia

patients due to the high costs associated with care. Patients with dementia may require specialized medical care, medication, and personal support, which can be expensive. Additionally, caregivers may need to take time off work or reduce their work hours to provide care, leading to a loss of income. Caregivers may also face unexpected expenses related to their loved one's care, such as home modifications or transportation costs. Overall, the financial burden of caring for someone with dementia can be significant and create stress for caregivers.

Table 8. *Examples of Emergent Theme: Adapting to Situational Changes*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	"Time management" (Participant 1 Transcript A Line 70)	Managing Stressors
5	"Alam mo yung galing ka na sa buong araw na pagod sabay pag-uwi is pagod pa rin." (Participant 5 Transcript E Line 37-38)	
9	"Yung pagod emotionally saka physically. Sa sitwasyon ko magkaakibat talaga siya at sobrang hirap masanay. Yun yung hanggang ngayon pilit kong kontrolin." (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 61- 62)	Lining up for possible source of assistance
2	"Yung changes po kasi long time na siya and siguro nagstart po yun sa pag prioritize sa lola ko kaysa sa sarili ko po" (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 53-54)	
3	"Sacrificing my needs para lang unahin yung needs ng father ko" (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 51)	
5	"kapag umuwi ako dati siya sumasalubong sakin tapos may naka ready ng pagkain" (Participant 5 Transcript E Line 39)	There's a practice of sacrificing oneself for the patient
7	"yung daily routine talaga since ito yung nabago ng buong buo" (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 37)	Difficulties in the daily routine
8	"yung paghingi ng tulong sa isa't-isa " (Participant 8 Transcript H Line 71)	Lining up for possible source of assistance
6	"Yung paghahanap ng resources, kasi hindi talaga sapat yung trabaho ko kaya minsan napunta kami sa city hall" (Participant 6 Transcript F Line 37-39)	
10	"We had difficulty in the adverse changes on the healthcare planning" (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 57-58)	
4	"Yung may makasama sa bahay na may dementia, parang nag-aalaga ka kasi ng bata kapag sila kasama mo " (Participant 4 Transcript D Line 53-54)	Incapability of the patient to do task
6	"si papa kasi nung kabataan naman niya sobrang sharp ng mind niya" (Participant 6 Transcript F Line 40)	Incapability of the patient to do task
7	"Maaaring hindi na talaga siya mag respond sa lahat ng bagay at kinakatakot ko yun kasi pwedeng ako hindi niya ma-recognize bigla niyang masaktan, nakakamiss din talaga yung dati na makita ko siyang malakas" (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 39-40)	

Participant 1 believes that time management is their main worry when a scenario changes. Participant 5 deals with their weariness from solving the problem they run across. Participant 1 and participant 5 had similar problems controlling their stressors in the context of the situation they encountered. On the other hand, Participant 9 Struggle in adjusting to emotional and physical changes in caring for Major Neurocognitive patient. Handling dementia patients can be stressful because their condition can cause them to behave in unpredictable ways, and their needs can be constant and demanding, which can be emotionally and physically exhausting for caregivers.

Participants 2 and 3 have always struggled with putting their personal needs second to the needs of the patient. For the love of the patients, they both gave their all. This would indicate that caregivers are having Difficulties adapting to Caregiving and personal life balance because it's hard to find life equilibrium in the situation they are dealing with.

Participant 5 is concerned about situational changes that take place during their predicament and lead to the patient's attachment and love for the caregiver disappearing.

The challenges of the everyday routine are being faced by participants 7, 8, and 6. Participants in a given reference group had the same concerns. Participant 6 struggles with asking for help, something participant 8 also experienced, and needs finding a potential source of aid.

According to Participant 4 caring for patient with Major Neurocognitive Disorder can be compare to nursing a child. The loss of Cognitive skill been one of the situations changes that the caregiver need to face off. Participant 6 is used to thinking of the patient loss of Intellectual ability.

Participant 9 found it difficult to adjust to both physical and emotional stress. The identical routine situational alterations were expressed by participant 7. One of Participant 7's wishes was for the patient to be as strong as before.

Participant 2 claimed that their circumstance was affected by adapting to healthcare planning. It is clear that the participant is aware of the challenges presented by adverse healthcare planning changes for all Major Neurocognitive patients and their caregivers who must deal with everyday challenges.

Table 9. *Examples of Emergent Theme: Situational Realization of the Existence of Anticipatory Grief*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
2	"Parang kahit nakikita ko po siya, parang wala na rin kasi hindi na po tulad ng dati na nakakausap ko pa" (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 62-63)	Inability to feel the presence of the patient even when seen physically
5	"kahit nandyan sya para wala na. may mga oras na kailangan itakbo sa ospital kasi may other na sakit pa, sobrang nakakapanghina" (Participant 5 Transcript E Line 45-46)	
6	"humihingi ako ng tulong at nagmamakaawa ako, parang yung feeling ko is life and death situation na yung condition, sobrang kaba, takot, at pigil hininga talaga" (Participant 6 Transcript F Line 43-45)	
4	"Salitang dementia pa lang ang unang pumapasok na sa isip ko is pagkawala" (Participant 4 Transcript D Line 67)	Major Neurocognitive Disorder transcends the occurrence of "lose."
7	"Hinang hina na rin ako at parang mawawala na siya kaya pray lang ako ng pray palagi para hindi niya ako pabayaan sa laban na ito." (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 52-53)	
10	"I knew I was grieving when even though I try my best to be optimistic, I get hit by emotions as such" (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 66-69)	
8	"one morning, nagpanic ako kasi hindi ko siya mahanap sa bahay turns out sinama pala siya pumasyal ng kapatid ko tas after that, talagang umiyak ako" (Participant 8 Transcript H L 82-84)	Situation that triggered the participant to think they are grieving.
7	"paano ko ba sasabihin, ahm, iniisip ko na kasi yung pagkawala niya kahit nandyan pa siya kasi hindi ko na rin naman talaga siya maramdaman" (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 44-46)	
5	"Siguro yung thought na "gawin mo na lahat para makapagpaalam ng maayos, before pa mawala" (Participant 5 Transcript E Line 42-43)	The respondent felt in a rush of providing everything before it's too late.
3	"kinakausap ko na siya in a way na parang nagpapaalam. I am assuring him na kahit ano man ang mangyari ay nasa maayos ng kalagayan kami" (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 60-62)	
1	"Madalas na naiiyak ako sa mga thoughts na hindi pa naman nangyayari" (Participant 1 Transcript A Line 80)	
7	"may mga oras na may tantrums siya, nafufustrate ako kasi wala akong magawa kundi habaan ang pasensya at pakalmahin siya" (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 46-47)	
9	"Narealize ko sigurong na para na rin akong nagggrieve pag ayaw ko siya mawaglit sa paningin ko. Ayaw kong mahiwalay ng matagal kay nanay" (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 72-74)	
6	"The part when I begged" (Participant 6 Transcript F Line 43)	

Participant 2. Inability to feel the presence of the patient even when seen physically. This would mean that the physical is still present but the psychological well-being of the patient is gradually losing. It transcribed with anticipatory grieving due to the changes and fatal situation of the patient.

Participants 5 and 6 claims that when they are in a position where their loved one is in danger of dying, they experience anticipatory grieving. When the patient is admitted to the hospital for an underlying disease, Participant 5 described it. Similar to participant 6, who experienced hopelessness and life-threatening circumstances.

Participants 4 and 7 also characterized the illness as lost. This would suggest that they develop this experience of anticipatory grief and that Major Neurocognitive illness transcends the occurrence of "loss." the anxiety of losing their loved ones brought on by cognitive dissonance.

Participant 10, Participant 8, and Participant 7 are apprehensive with the feeling of grief and death of patient. Participant 10 knew they are grieving when unexpectedly being pessimistic despite the attempt to be positive. Similar with the situation of participant 7 when the patient's presence is still there but the caregiver develops the thoughts of death and nothingness surface. Participant 8 had Situation that triggered the participant to think they are grieving. This would indicate that if a loved one has a life-threatening illness such as neurocognitive disorder, a family member or close relative may experience anticipatory grief at any point from the initial onset of symptoms to the time of the diagnosis to when they enter hospice care.

For Participant 5, Participant 3, and Participant 1 they know that they are grieving when they anticipate that death will occur so they need to do everything for the patient before the occurrence of the death. Participant 5 stated that they felt in a rush of providing everything before it's too late. Similar with Participant 3 when Farewell messages filled with assurance. Within the particular reference Participant 1 expressed the same Issues. Emotional over thoughts about the prospect of the patient's condition.

According to Participant 7, Participant 9, and Participant 6 they develop helplessness and grieving during the situation of caring for patient with Major Neurocognitive Disorder. Participant 7 experienced frustration at being completely helpless during tantrums. This implies that the caregiver think that everything will just lead to lose since the situation are getting worse. Participant 9 went to the point that they do not want to be away from the patient for a long duration because they know that the life of the patient won't be longer. Helplessness has also been identified according to participant 6 when he begged for help.

Table 10. *Examples of Emergent Theme: Coping Strategies of Filipino Family Caregivers*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	“dumating man sa punto na miski ako hindi maalala, iisipin ko na lang na laman pa rin ako ng puso niya dahil kahit papaano nakita naman niya kung paano ko siya pagsilbihan kahit noon pa man na wala pa siyang sakit” (Participant 1 Transcript A Line 91-92)	The respondents find comfort in providing care for the patient
4	“naniniwala ako na mahal naman talaga niya ako kasi never naman niya ako pinabayaan. Kaya kahit makakalimot na siya, na-cocomfort ako sa idea na napagsilbihan ko pa rin siya” (Participant 4 Transcript D Line 72-73).	
2	“hinding hindi po namin siya susukuan at papabayaan, hanggang ngayon sinusubukan po namin gawin yung mga paborito niyang gawin dati pero this time with proper guidance na po talaga naming” (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 71-72)	Spending time doing the patient's previous hobbies alongside the patient
9	“parang nagiging sort of coping ko na or namin ni nanay yung pagluluto. Bukod sa hilig niya, parang enjoying the good little time ganoon” (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 80-81).	
3	“I always show him pictures, lagi ko siyang binubuklatan ng album namin tapos ikukwento ko sa kanya kung ano yung mga nangyari behind that picture, nagiging way ko na rin yun para makaramdam ng connection sa kanya kahit hindi na nagresponse ng maayos” (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 70-71)	Filipino family caregivers establish a bond with the patient through past memories
6	“binabasahan ko siya nung mga past memories sa diary niya, parang way naming yun ng pag uusap kasi nakikita kong nakikinig siya sa akin” (Participant 6 Transcript F Line 49-50).	
5	“through praying, talagang nilelet go ko na lahat ng worries at burdens ko kay Lord” (Participant 5 Transcript E Line 49)	Filipino family caregivers hold on to their spiritual beliefs and practices
7	“Kumakapit na lang talaga ako ngayon kay Lord at sa pamilya ko na bigyan ako ng lakas para kayanin lahat” (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 50-51).	
8	“I talk my worries out to other people. Parang venting ba or release ng worries” (Participant 8 Transcript H Line 89-90).	The respondent talks with other people about their situation
10	“I'd like to think she is also still doing her best to see the world through her eyes and trying to respond to the "feeling" behind the behavior” (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 76-78)	The Filipino family caregiver tries to comprehend how the patient thinks

Caregiving brings comfort to the Filipino family caregivers

The Filipino family caregivers are aware that patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders experience memory loss in spite of the use of medications and other treatments. As shared by Participant 1, even if the patient eventually loses the ability to recognize him, he will still feel at ease knowing the fact that the patient was able to identify him and see his efforts as a caregiver before the condition worsened. Similar to how participant 4 experienced it, giving care also brings comfort to the caregivers.

Spends quality time with the patient

Patients with an impending death are encouraged to make the most of their remaining time; this urges the Filipino family caregivers to interact with the patient more frequently. Participant 2 claims that one of their coping mechanisms is to get the patient involved in something they enjoyed doing before being told they had the disorder. Participant 9 gave the example of spending quality time with the patient while cooking meals.

Reminiscing the past memories with the patient

When memories are searched for, they can be found. Recalling old memories and having a conversation with the patient about them helps the Filipino family caregivers cope with the pain of being forgotten by a loved one who has a serious neurocognitive disorder. According to Participant 3, a photo album is very helpful for fostering a conversation with the patient and cultivating a sense of closeness. The same goes for Participant 6, who is reading the patient's diary, which contains written memories, like a storybook.

Be dependent on spiritual principles and practices

The culture of the Philippines makes religion an integral part of Filipinos' daily lives, and Filipinos are renowned for their unwavering spiritual principles and practices which would imply that Filipinos frequently turn to the supreme being for assistance and direction when experiencing immense pain. According to Participant 5, they offer prayers as a way of releasing their burdens and worries. Similar

to Participant 7, seeks support from the Lord and his family.

Talking with others to express one's situation

Being a caregiver for a patient with a fatal illness imposes enormous stressors, which frequently lead to anxiety and depression. This commonly necessitates the caregiver having someone on whom to rely or even converse. Being present for one another is part of the Filipino cultural value of "Pagdadamayan." This implies that Filipino family caregivers shared their experiences with someone as a way to release the emotions that burdened them, which is exactly what Participant 8 is talking about.

Empathizing with the Patient's Condition

Understanding the patient's condition is one of the most effective coping strategies for the caregivers because it prevents the caregiver from overthinking and becoming frustrated by the uncontrollable situation. According to Participant 10, there is nothing that can be done to bring back the past, and it is essential to put oneself in the shoes of the patient in order to comprehend the world in which the patient lives while dealing with the disorder.

Table 11. *Examples of Emergent Theme: Anticipatory Grief among Filipino Family Caregivers*

Participant No.	Specific Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	"Nagagawa ko na yung mga gusto ko gawin for her. I can buy more time para mabigay yung mga gusto niya, and maparanas yung mga hindi pa niya naexperience. Somehow, iniisip ko na mawala man siya, at least nagawa ko lahat" (Participant 1 Transcript A Line 96-97)	Anticipatory grief gives caregivers a chance to fulfil the patient's needs
3	"Unlike sa sakit ng iba, biglaan at walang maayos na farewell, parang huli na lahat. Pero here sa case ni papa, I'm very lucky na naalagaan ko pa, nabibigay ko pa needs niya, lahat lahat" (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 75-77)	
2	"Hmm.. siguro po yung nasasabi ko na po at napapakita kung gaano po ako ka-thankful sa kanya sa lahat ng nagawa niya po for me" (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 75-76)	Anticipatory grief encourages caregivers to express their feelings about the patient
4	"Yung grieving or pagpapaalam napapa-process agad siya ng maaga, parang nagkakaroon ng linaw sa isipan ko kung ano yung mga dapat gawin habang nandyan pa siya" (Participant 4 Transcript D Line 76-78)	Enable the respondents to plan ahead for the patient
8	"We got to fulfill yung gusto namin family to make his memory worthwhile" (Participant 8 Transcript H Line 98-99)	
5	"inaalis niya ako sa possibility na magsisi kasi what if kung ibang sakit yun and mas mabilis magprogress, tapos tuloy tuloy lang yung gawain ko na gumala, etc." (Participant 5 Transcript E Line 54-55)	The ability to anticipate grief enables the caregivers to protect themselves from guilt brought on by neglecting the patient
6	"Pre-loss grieving helps me to accept that death is inevitable. Talagang kapag oras na ay oras na talaga. Sobrang uncertain kasi ng mga bagay sa ganitong sakit kaya dapat laging prepared" (Participant 6 Transcript F Line 53-55)	It teaches the respondent to accept the uncertainty of death
7	"Naiintroduce na agad yung mga worst case scenario and situations. Hindi siya biglaan na mawawala agad" (Participant 7 Transcript G Line 56-57)	Exposes respondents to the worst-case scenario of an MND patient's reality
9	"Para sa akin nakakatulong yung pre-loss grieving ba? Oo nakakatulong siya kasi mas nagiging realistic ako compared to before" (Participant 9 Transcript I Line 86-87)	
10	"But I guess it helped in a way that it made me more appreciative of the time we have left to enjoy together" (Participant 10 Transcript J Line 82-83)	It teaches the respondent to become appreciative of the time and presence of the patient

Provides opportunity to fulfill patient's needs
 Anticipatory grief causes a person to go through an early grief process that influences the person's thinking and behavior to correspond with the patient's condition. The experience of pre-loss grief, according to Participant 1, compels them to attend to the patient's needs. This is similar to Participant 3, who considers herself fortunate to be given time to do things for her father.

Encourage the caregivers to be vocal of about their feelings

Once the patient is in a situation where life or death is at stake, family members typically begin to express their feelings towards the patient. Some people only express their feelings after the patient passes away, and they feel guilty for it because it is too late. When someone is experiencing anticipatory grief, they may express their feelings for the patient while they are still audible to them. Participant 2 mentioned that because they are afraid of being too late, it helps them to express their emotions while the patient can still hear and look at them.

Facilitates the outlining of plans designed for the patient

When caregivers become aware of the patient's condition, it mostly influences them to plan ahead of time what can be done to make the patient's memory worthwhile. This may be common among caregivers of other illnesses, but in the case of a Major Neurocognitive

Disorder, caregivers plan ahead of time due to the fear of uncertainty. As Participant 4 stated, it gives them plenty of time to consider the life experience that can be given to the patient. Meanwhile, Participant 8 employs the plans to fill the patient's memory with delightful experiences and recollections. Prevention of guilt being developed after the patient's death. When the caregivers realize their shortcomings towards the patients, guilt rises from within. This is due to their acts of neglect, inattentiveness, and disregard for the patient's needs. Meanwhile, anticipatory grief teaches Filipino family caregivers to do everything possible to avoid living with guilt after the patient dies. According to Participant 5, the experience motivates him to meet the needs of patients while they are still attainable Acceptance of the uncertainty. It is uncertain how the patient with a Major Neurocognitive Disorder will live their life, how their disorder will develop over time, and how these things will affect how they live. Along with this effect, it also has an impact on Filipino family caregivers who must deal with their fear of uncertain situations and potential outcomes. Pre-loss grief, in the opinion of Participant 6, helps people accept both the uncertainty of death and its inevitability. Exposure to the reality of patient's with Major Neurocognitive Disorder Anticipatory grief leads caregivers to discover the reality of a patient with a Major Neurocognitive Disorder. Their fear of uncertainty drives them to learn about the disorder. Exposure to the worst-case scenario raises caregiver's awareness. According to Participant 7, early introduction to the possible situation prepares Filipino family caregivers for what to expect and how they will react if symptoms begin to manifest. This is similar to Participant 9's emphasis on the role of anticipatory grief as an exposure to reality.

Encourage Filipino family caregivers to develop gratitude. Aside from the exposure, planning, and awareness that it brings, anticipatory grief also teaches the caregivers to be grateful for what is still there. It urged them to utilize the time and resources at hand to offer everything they could. There are some terminal illnesses that do not allow the family to spend the patient's remaining time with them because they require intensive medical care and hospitalization. Major Neurocognitive Disorders, on the other hand, allow the family caregiver to take care of the patient. With this reality, caregivers must experience and demonstrate gratitude. As shared by Participant 10, pre-loss grief helped her to appreciate the smallest things that they enjoy together with the patient.

The Caregiver's Relationship with the Patient

One underlying topic that centered around the caregiver and patient relationship emerged from the clustered meaning. This section made clear that caring for others can have good effects, especially if the person is caring for a loved one.

Improving Relationship

Some family caregivers describe positive caring experiences, saying that having the knowledge that their loved one is receiving excellent care gives their lives more meaning. The experience of taking care of a seriously ill patient gave them a sense of progress and made them stronger and more responsible. According to the respondent,

"Yung time na di pa sya nadiagnose sa sakit nya we act normal po na mag-ina ung typical lang po. I honor and obey my parents pero nung magkasakit sya mas madami po akong nagawang maganda bilang isang anak sa kanya " (Participant 9).

According to the study by Branger (2019), the researcher found that managing people with severe cognitive impairment and having a genetic connection to dementia patients are the most significant predictors of higher caregiving satisfaction. This is comparable to respondent 9's experience, who said that taking care of his loved ones gave him a feeling of positive caregiving fulfillment.

Personal Development as a Caregiver

Caregiving for a loved one requires a significant life change. Even if it comes with a lot of responsibilities, such a significant transition can also present an opportunity to enhance your own life. The various abilities developed through practice, which can also result in a great deal of satisfaction, are among the advantages of caregiving.

"Honestly feel ko I developed my purpose of becoming her daughter." (Participant 10).

A concept known as caring appraisal, according to a study conducted by J Caring Sci (2018), explains how caregivers see or interpret both the good and unpleasant aspects of the caregiving experience. Individuals who play a life function like caring are often expected to receive and benefit from appraisals. Caregiving is generally viewed unfavorably, yet there are benefits to caring, with caregivers expressing personal gain and happiness in their roles. Although favorable outcomes of being a caregiver for someone with dementia are less frequently studied, this study is comparable to studies that have produced the theme that caring for someone with dementia also has beneficial results.

Acceptance of the Caregiver in Patients Conditions

The clustered meaning revealed one underlying theme that was concerned with the caregivers' acceptance of the patient with Major Neurocognitive Disorder. According to the developed accumulating theme, the majority of caregivers find it difficult to accept the patient's condition.

Acceptance Difficulties for Caregivers

The respondents find it challenging to accept a patient who has been diagnosed Major Neurocognitive Disorder, just as the patient. Processing the news, adjusting to the new situation, and grieving one's losses all take time. As mentioned by the respondent.

“Ahm,sa una kasi hindi pa naman nagsi-sink in sa akin yung bigat ng sakit niya. Actually, nung narinig ko from her doctor na may dementia siya ang unang nasa isip ko lang is magiging makalimutin na siya. Pero the moment na nalaman ko na yung iba pang impact and possible outcomes ng sakit niya doon ako biglang tinamaan ng reality. Hmm, it took me months before ko matanggap yung adjustments na mangyayari sa buhay ko and ang nagiging motivation ko lang talaga is yung love ko sa mother ko”. (Participant 1).

Kim et al.'s (2016) study found that family caregivers find it challenging to watch a member of their family suffer from dementia because they are unsure of how the disease will develop as well as how to lower the risk of dementia and alter their current lifestyle. The study provides a basic foundation for understanding dementia-related anxiety for family caregivers of a loved one with dementia. The study's findings, which show that not just persons with Major Neurocognitive Disorder may find it difficult to accept their diagnosis, are connected to the topics in this literature. Friends and family members, especially those who are providing care for the person, frequently experience this predicament. This can mean that the family caregiver needs some time to get ready to consider the likelihood that the patient has a serious condition.

Unawareness among Caregivers

Lack of comprehension and care skills of the disorder influences how respondents deal with their current circumstances. The majority of caregivers said they lacked the knowledge and skills necessary to provide effective care, that their information needs were not being met, and that they feared this would hurt the patient. As shared by the respondent,

“Parang hindi ako dumaan sa processing ng thoughts kung ready na ba ako, tanggap ko ba, makakaya ko ba. Kasi nung day na nagkaalaman, rekta ako agad ang nag step-up for my father. Kaya may mga sudden outbursts ako ng emotions kapag nahahirapan ako sa pag-aalaga kasi hindi naman ako dumaan sa ganoon, hindi ko naproseso ng maayos yung mga changes, tumalon ako agad”. (Participant 6).

In accordance with WHO (2012) article, this serves as a timely reminder of the significance of prioritizing the needs of the family caregiver, who is a crucial resource in long-term care arrangements for the person with dementia. This is related to the study's findings that taking on the role of a family caregiver can be challenging, particularly if there is a lack of knowledge and understanding of dementia that creates barriers to diagnosis and care and negatively affects the caregivers on a physical, psychological, and financial basis.

Caregiving as a Purpose

Some family caregivers feel motivated to offer care out of a sense of love and fulfillment because they consider it as their job to take care of their loved ones, even though it can be difficult to accept the patient's position. As mentioned by respondent,

“Hmm, hindi ko na po namalayan kasi ang naging mindset ko ay alagaan lang lola ko tapos tumatak na po sa akin yung worry na baka one day hindi na po niya ako maalala, malaking tulong din po talaga yung pag uwi ni mama”. (Participant 2).

Family members have always been expected to be the ones charged with providing primary care to the patients in the family. This could be the patient's spouse, children, or remaining relatives who have been living with the person prior to when the illness was diagnosed and provide unpaid care (Brodsky & Donkin, 2022).

Accumulated Daily Concerns of Caregivers and its Effects

The clustered formed one emergent theme that revolves around the daily concerns of Filipino family caregivers and its effects on their caregiving. There were 8 daily concerns have been developed as a result of the data analysis and are discussed in this section.

Adapting and Learning the Nature of Major Neurocognitive Disorder

The participants indicated that their regular concern has been a lack of knowledge about the disorders' symptoms and a lack of learning resources needed for further understanding the patient's disease. As stated by two of the participants,

" My daily thoughts consist of continuous learning and adapting to the changes that I experience taking care of my mother. Instead of dwelling too much on thinking of the hopelessness we have, I want to understand how we can provide best care for her. Pinipilit ko makahanap ng solusyon kahit sinabing incurable siya and yung memory loss is inevitable" “We really had a lack of knowledge about his condition that made it hard for us to realize how worse the illness is. Kung nagkaroon siguro kami ng knowledge about sa magiging pwede niyang sakit bago pa siya madiagnose, siguro mas nakapaghanda kami.” (Participant 3) Another participant added, " Araw-araw iniisip ko kung paanong paraan ako magiging effective na caregiver para kay mama. Kung paano ko mapprovide yung pag-aalaga na angkop para sakanya. daily thoughts consist of continuous learning and adapting to the changes that I experience taking care of my mother" (Participant 10)

Recent studies indicate that Major Neurocognitive Disorder is the final stage of the progressive and incurable disease. However, there has been minimal exploration into how family members perceive their loved ones' condition in advanced stages of the disorder. According to the study by Andrews et al., (2015), the majority of family members lacked an intellectual understanding of dementia's fatal nature. They had limited access to formal knowledge since they relied on lay understandings and were unable to recognize a link between dementia and death. Furthermore, despite their relative's severe stage of disease, most family members failed to participate in

thorough discussions with healthcare providers about these difficulties. As a result, healthcare providers must prioritize improving family members' understanding of dementia progression through effective communication strategies such as establishing partnerships between employees and caregivers focused on shared education about end-of-life planning during advanced stages of disease progression.

According to a study by Nunns (2015), which focused on the everyday experiences of family caregivers caring for dementia patients who were near death, dementia cases receive little knowledge and attention because it is thought of as a common condition among the elderly. This theme emphasizes the significance of timely regular diagnosis and planning for both dementia patients and family members.

Fear of Patient's Death

Patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder, tend to be looked after at home by relatives. Therefore, caring for a relative struggling with the disease can be a challenging and difficult experience. In studies on family caregivers of dementia patients, there hasn't been much focus on death anxiety. As a person with the disease could die soon within years of being diagnosed, family caregivers can develop death anxiety out of fear of witnessing the person they care for pass away. One participant stated,

"Sa totoo lang po madami ako inaalala pero pinaka naapektuhan ako through being afraid of her death." "Yung way of living ng family ko is nagbago kasi from minding our own naging center na ng attention naming yung pag aalaga kay mama" Lagi akong nag-aalala baka Magaya siya sa mga napapanood ko through own research na yung iba iltimo paghinga nang tama nakakalimutan nila. Ganoon. (Participant 1)

Several researchers have found that caring for relatives with dementia has negative consequences on the caregiver's physical and emotional health during the caregiving period. However, less attention has been paid to caregiver's emotional state after the patient's death. When the absence of a family member is unclear, the stressor event or situation is referred to as ambiguous loss. Ambiguous Loss Theory by Boss (2002) provides theoretical foundation for the study. This stressor circumstance arises when a person to whom one is emotionally attached is physically present but psychologically absent; that is, "here but not here". One example of a family caregiver experiencing psychological ambiguous loss is Major Neurocognitive Disorder. This is a psychological loss, such as a mental or emotional disappearance (such as when someone's personality has changed so profoundly that they no longer appear to be the person you previously knew).

Loneliness and Helplessness

Family caregivers may have psychological benefits from taking care of or family member, but they may also face challenges that may have a detrimental impact on their quality of life and their mental and physical health. One major challenge that caregivers experience is loneliness, which has been linked to the patients' illness and early death. One participant stated,

"Dalawa po iniinda ko noon, yung pagiging mag-isa pati po yung sakit ni lola. Dahil kami lang po sa bahay magkasama and madalas po hindi siya nakikipagusap unless ako po magiinitiate ng conversation samin pakiramdam ko po mag-isa lang ako lagi. Helpless din naman po kasi di naman po kasalanan ni lola yun. Ayaw ko naman din po iburden yung ibang mga kamag-anak namin or even my friends sa pagvent out sakanila kasi hindi din naman nila ganoon ka maiintindihan yung weight nung situation ko." (Participant 2)

One theme emerged from the study by Vasileiou et al. (2015) that emphasizes how family caregivers' feelings of helplessness and loneliness were frequently seen to be connected to the limitations that the caregiving the scenario enforced. Loneliness was associated with feelings of helplessness and ineffectiveness when caregivers face difficult caregiving moments and when help from others was not readily available, as well as an overall sense of helplessness in enhancing the caregiving situation. A greater sense of sole obligation for the well-being of the patient was also suggested as a background for identifying emotions of loneliness.

Challenge in Time Management and Organization of Priorities

Participants frequently expressed how their daily lives changed and were defined by restricted freedom to define own time and choice of space, lack of freedom, and very few chances to be at ease with concerns. The patients' needs and well-being were a constant worry and priority, whereas time spent away from them required extensive preparation on the part of the caregiver. Four particular individuals expressed the same concern and noted,

"Isa po sa mga nagbago sa pang-araw-araw ko is yung sa time po. May mga araw po noon na wala akong maayos na tulog kaya lagi po akong nahuhuli sa pagpasok" (Participant 2). "Non-stop yung mga thoughts na what if i-try ko ito, yan, yun, kasi desperate talaga ako na mapagaling siya. Umabot pa sa nakakapasa na ako ng late sa work outputs" (Participant 5)". "Iniisip ko rin na hanggang saan kakayanin ng my own family yung situation namin sa bahay kasi pati talaga sila affected." (Participant 7) "Nasubukan talaga yung pagiging anak saka pagiging ina ko at the same time. I had to juggle my tasks. Naging kumbaga 50/50 ako sa parehas kong responsibilidad" (Participant 9).

As the Major Neurocognitive Disorder progresses, family caregiver strain arises. This would imply that the caregiver's position must be modified to fit the demands of the patients, regardless of the repercussions for their personal lives, because the objective of caregiving is to respond to the patients' needs. (Hazzan, et al. 2022). In addition to supporting with daily routines such as bathing, dressing, and

eating, family caregivers frequently perform medical or nursing chores that are typically handled by nurses. Family caregivers encounter common challenges that cause them to feel overwhelmed, worried and intimidated by their responsibilities. Caregivers frequently find themselves with less time for other family members and themselves. Caregivers frequently spend a great deal of time taking care of the patient that they end up sacrificing fun activities like hobbies or vacations and even work priorities. Caregivers frequently devote so much time to caring chores that they have lost touch with friends and family outside the home. Additionally, a family caregiver may struggle to get adequate sleep because the patient's sleep-wake pattern is usually unpredictable. Sleep deprivation can be especially harmful to a caregiver who is already stressed from working long hours. (American Senior Communities, 2022)

Collective Emotional and Physical Stress

Caregivers of patients suffering from Major Neurocognitive Disorders have physical, emotional, and financial challenges. The overall health of caregivers can be affected as a result of the demands of the caregiving. A family caregiver is responsible for providing and handling patient who requires long-term care. Caregiving for a loved one with a Major Neurocognitive problem is more challenging than looking after people of a different chronic disease or impairment. Therefore, caregivers are more likely to provide more hours to support patients with personal daily tasks, protect them from harm, deal with disturbed behaviors. These responsibilities exhaust caretakers and expose them to illness linked to stress. Three participants stated,

"Nasubukan talaga yung pagiging anak saka pagiging ina ko at the same time. I had to juggle my tasks. Naging kumbaga 50/50 ako sa parehas kong responsibilidad " (Participant 9). Another participant expressed, "Na-stress talaga ako ng malala and iba siya when it comes to burden" (Participant 3) "the most noticeable effect it had sa family namin is yung emotional saka physical na stress talaga" (Participant 8)

According to Sörensen & Conwell, (2011), Major Neurocognitive Disorder has an enormous effect not only on patients who have been diagnosed with the condition, but also on their loved ones who confront the challenges of providing physical care and emotional support associated with chronic disease. Caregivers are obligated to acquiring the skills required to deal with the individual's interpersonal demands when their cognition diminishes. Caregiving can be an overwhelming experience, especially because family caregivers are closely associated with the patient and have no formal expertise. Seeing a loved one change rapidly before their eyes has a negative impact on their physical and mental health. Caregiver burnout is caused by a variety of circumstances, including psychological, emotional, social, and financial challenges. Psychological morbidity refers to the stress, despair, and anxiety that the caregiver may experience and is the number one predictor of quality of life among caregivers, according to Jorge et al. (2019).

Consideration for Nursing Homes and MND Community Support Groups

The decision on whether to institutionalize a patient with Major Neurocognitive Disorder is complicated and contingent upon both patient and caregiver characteristics. Disorders such as Major Neurocognitive Disorder, are characterized by a significant cognitive decline interfering with independence. Thus, individuals who have cognitive problems will increasingly require help and care to manage to live a normal everyday life at home. Family caregivers serve an integral part in this environment, therefore formal support is required to reduce unmet requirements and improve caregiving. One participant stated,

"May mga times na tumitingin ako ng mga facilities na nag-aalaga sa mga tulad niya. I considered na to send him sa mga ganoon" (Participant 4) Another participant stated, "naghanap hanap ako ng community groups or support para magkaroon naman ng idea kung paano ihahandle yung patient" "magmula noon hindi na ako masyado nag ooverthink" (Participant 6)

According to a literature by Soilemezi et al., (2017). The home setting is critical for dementia caregivers. It is essential for people of all cultures and ages, but especially for the elderly, as it is the major aging habitat. It serves as a place of security, shelter, and sanctuary for the self, integrating the previous experiences and retaining self-identity. Caregivers must decide whether to move their loved one to more supportive accommodation, switch their present home dementia-friendly, or care for their relative at home. Furthermore, most caregivers consider nursing homes as for in-patient care for Major Neurocognitive Disorder, can covers up to PHP10,000 in hospital expenses through PhilHealth which includes the healthcare facilities and provider's professional fees. However, to be eligible for these benefits, certain criterias must be met first. Soilemezi et al. (2017) share research about the shifting sense of home for dementia caregivers. On the other hand, support groups for those who care for patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder are potentially beneficial in a variety of aspects. Connecting with others in a similar circumstance can provide people with comfort, understanding, expertise, and support. Support groups serve as outlets for people facing similar challenges to share their stories, get advice from those who can relate, and provide and receive encouragement.

Everyday Challenges on becoming a Caregiver

Patients suffering from Major Neurocognitive Disorder require continuous assistance. They may be unable to move or perform personal care, have difficulties eating, are susceptible to illnesses, and are unable to express their requirements. Hallucinations, confusion, incontinence, and mood issues are some extremely typical symptoms. A caregiver's obligation is likely to include new problems such as coping with unpleasant feelings of grief and loss. One participant stated,

"iniisip ko na lang kung paano namin kakayanin yung pang-araw-araw na challenges ng pag-aalaga gawa na nga ng mayroon na din akong sariling pamilya. Simula kasi nung nadiagnose siya, parang everyday mayroon kaming bagong scenario ganoon. Kumbaga di

na ako nagkakaroon time to plan ahead para sa mga bagay bagay kasi nagiging at the moment lang ako lagi. "(Participant 9)

According to the World Health Organization (2021), the caregiver develops methods of interaction to establish a plan of action, and they provide the patient with meals, clothing, and other essentials. The patient appears to have trouble getting around, greater demands for help, and may exhibit unexpected outbursts of aggressiveness and reckless behavior in the severe stage. Therefore, Caregivers dedicate their whole attention to the patient at this stage, requiring assistance with feeding, bathing, dressing, and mobility. Additionally, this highlighted the diverse experiences and effects that caregivers may encounter during the course of caregiving. This further contributes to the prevalent perception of dementia caregivers as invisible victims of the terminal disease.

Financial Strain

The Major Neurocognitive Disorder has an impact on caregivers and society, resulting in increased healthcare expenses. In addition, the Philippines is dealing with the crisis, and significant preparedness is required to deal with the problem properly. One participant stated,

"it was hard for us to adjust financially. Lagi ko iniisip yung time na to admit him to professional healthcare providers para maavail din yung PhilHealth assistance" (Participant 8) Another participant stated, "Kaya naman naging daily thoughts ko na yung possibilities na lumala yung sa mother ko and makulangan ako ng resources" (Participant 1)

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, 3,368 people died as a result of the condition between 2012 and 2018. It is an evolving problem that will continue to escalate in the future years. Therefore, raising awareness and advocating for improved health care and societal solutions to combat the epidemic is vital. Currently, PhilHealth does not cover for diagnosis and management in outpatient settings. The average cost of Alzheimer's disease diagnosis and treatment, including assessment, laboratory, rehabilitation sessions, caregiver education, and drugs, is projected to be Php 100,000. All of the above amenities come with a 20% senior citizen discount. The Department of Health Philippines does not have data on the number of people working in mental health care, but each regional health unit has at least one health staff member in charge of the mental health program. There is also a void in the monitoring of health-care structure. In addition, there is no database or monitoring of the health workforce for either public or private dementia facilities. De la Vega, Garcia, and Torreblanca, (2018).

Concept of Becoming a Caregiver and its Considerations

The implications of caring for a relative with Major Neurocognitive Disorder at home are challenging for caregivers. Multiple themes emerged throughout the focus specifically on caregiver involvement in the context of the meaning and experience of the caregiving role.

Personal Choice: Caregiving is a Form of Love

Despite the challenges associated with the obligation, caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder, represent great love. The caregiving relationship is founded on feelings of devotion and love. Caregivers may be grasped into the role unexpectedly when a loved one is diagnosed with an unexpected medical problem. The caregivers may at first respond based on emotional bonds in either case. A participant stated,

" Syempre personal choice ko siya kasi mother ko yun eh, handa ako magpaka-kahit na ano para sa nanay ko. Para sa akin being a caregiver is a greatest form of love" (Participant 1) Another participant stated, "Ito yung tinatawag na unconditional love kasi wala akong hininging kapalit from him, hindi ko nagawang magsumbat at magalit." (Participant 4) Another participant stated the similar message, "pagiging caregiver is a devotion of your love" (Participant). Another participant stated, "It serves as a true meaning of a family, yung hindi mag iiwanan hanggang tumanda at mamatay man " "kasi ang pagiging family caregiver ay bukal dapat sa loob. " (Participant 6)

In a study by Tönnies's (2002) to introduce the Gemeinschaft and Gesellschaft concepts in 1887, it was deemed helpful to understand the disturbances experienced by family caregivers. Tönnies characterized Gemeinschaft as the way relationships worked in a traditional family-based culture, where the individual was submissive to the family and owed a limitless amount of assistance to other family members. Family caregivers also strive to uphold Gemeinschaft ideals, but the Gesellschaft circumstances of contemporary society leave family caregivers with insufficient conditions for upholding the endless Gemeinschaft obligations as people live independently, minding their own affairs at a comparable time as individuals live longer and as more patients live with Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Major Neurocognitive Disorder leads Family Members to Become Immediate Caregivers through Kinship and Connection

Occasionally, individuals become caregivers over time most typically through children or a spouse who observes a partner's forgetfulness, and even after diagnosis. The caregiver may not see themselves as the caregiver at first, but as time passes, the caregiver's reliance on support for many activities of daily living may expand, causing the caregiver to willingly acquire a more expansive focus on a loved one's needs. Eight participant stated similar response,

"It serves as a true meaning of a family, yung hindi mag iiwanan hanggang tumanda at mamatay man " "kasi ang pagiging family caregiver ay bukal dapat sa loob. " (Participant 6) Another participant stated "Syempre personal choice ko siya kasi mother ko yun eh,

handa ako magpaka-kahit na ano para sa Nanay" (Participant 1) "Personal choice ko siya kasi in the first place, tatay ko eh" (Participant 4) Further participants added, "Personal kong choice ito kasi since mahal ko parents ko" (Participant 9). "Hindi ko naman po pinili noon na maging ganyan pero dahil nagkasakit po lola ko at ako lang kasama niya, matic po na nauwi na rin sa ganyan" [From the word "family" talagang gagawin po ang lahat para po sa pamilya] (Participant 2). "It's another way of saying "mahal kita, aalagaan kita" yung pagiging family caregiver is also a self-sacrifice kasi mas pipiliin mo na iwanan yung mga nakasanayan mo at sumakay sa changes na mangyayari during caregiving" (Participant 5). "Yung pagiging family caregiver ko is a life changer talaga, babaguhin talaga niya lahat and it is something na wala naman akong magagawa" "ako lang nag iisa niyang anak, matanda na rin si mama para alagaan siya" (Participant 7)

Patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder are typically attended for by family members. Blood relatives have always been expected to provide primary care to patients in the family. This could be the patient's partner, children, or other surviving family members who were living with them before the sickness came to light and offer uncompensated care. (Brodaty & Donkin, 2022). Major Neurocognitive Disorder differ in their onset, symptoms, and influence not just on the patient, as well as on the entire family. Certain diseases necessitate minimal involvement from relatives because they are easily treated with medicine and therapy. However, for Major Neurocognitive Disorder, it needs utmost attention. Regardless of the conditions, becoming a family caregiver is a difficult position that most people are unprepared to take on and, like plenty of family caregivers, they were probably inexperienced for this situation. Most relatives, yet, believe family caring to be a more fulfilling experience—for both them and their loved one. Contradicts the Concept of "Utang na Loob"

Caregivers' perspectives on what caregiving entails and why it is necessary varies. For some, it was a matter of morals and whether or not it was the proper thing to do. Some caregivers thought that by providing care, they might give back to their relatives. According to one participant,

"I really want to reciprocate the love she gave us when we were young. " (Participant 10). Another participant added, "To be a family caregiver is more of a thought of "utang na loob, willingly ko sya inakong responsibility kasi alam ko ganun di yung naramdaman nilang bata pa ako. Yung sense of responsibility." (Participant 3)

Some caregivers' main motivations for providing care for their relatives with Major Neurocognitive Disorder were the chance to express their love and gratitude to their family members—typically their parents—and to repay the years of care they had received. Some believed they were repaying them for the love and attention they had earned. This intergenerational appreciation and recognition might be linked to cultural values, such as the value of familism, which is very important in Latino culture. (Scotland, 2015). In the Philippines, it is the concept known as "Utang na Loob" that essentially states that an individual who has received help or anything else from a relative must exhibit genuine pursuit and repay the favor with goodwill. This is common in Filipino family relationships, wherein children are obligated to help their parents with regularly living expenses after attending school and take responsibility the necessities for their family members needs until they get older.

Personal Decision due to Capabilities and Availability

In addition to engagement with the patient with Major Neurocognitive Disorder, another theme was determined as a consideration to caregiving duties and routines. Participants committed to devoting an extensive amount of their time and daily routine to the needs of the care recipient when they decided to care for their relatives at home. This included establishing a consistent daily pattern in which they completed all daily duties, monitoring treatments and drugs, examining new symptoms, and assuring safety. As they have the capability and time availability, the routine provided regularity for both the caregiver and the patient, and unexpected occurrences were more bearable within the constraints of the pattern. One participant alluded,

"nakikita ko rin naman talaga na mas may kakayahan ako para maalagaan at masuportahan siya kumpara sa iba naming mga kamag-anak." (Participant 3) Another participant added, "Yes, it's a personal choice. When our family discussed it parang considering everyone's lifestyle ako yung pinakacapable in terms of time availability and personal responsibilities" (Participant 8)

Caregivers often pointed out, one never knows what would happen in terms of behavioral, emotional, or physical challenges would arise at any given moment—and thus they tried to accept the situation and focus on the caregiving role. On top of carefully reading the materials, some caregivers were diligently researching pertinent subjects on the Internet. Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients and their family caregivers requires time, an organized strategy, and assistance from a variety of professionals and care providers. Lang et al., 2017; Lethin et al., 2019; Olsen et al., 2018 (2016). All of these strategies, at both the individual and family levels, are critical, given that the home is frequently the preferred place of care, especially in the early and middle stages of dementia, due to its ability to ensure quality, well-being, full consideration for preferences, and the effectiveness of costs. (Broda et al., 2017; Clarkson et al., 2017; Kerpershoek et al., 2018).

Filipino Family Caregivers' Emotional Outcomes as the Disorder Advances to Severity Phase

The data analysis produced clusters of formulated meanings that emerged into one theme that discusses the emotional impact of experience towards caregiving brought on by uncertainty and the concept of anticipatory grief. Filipino family caregivers were found to be suffering from five emotional crises with their caregiving experience towards patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Frustration

People are often frustrated by the lack of options for finding a solution. The Filipino people, in particular, are known to be problem solvers, seeking and even resorting to extreme measures just to fix or manage things in their lives. Family caregivers who have a patient with a Major Neurocognitive Disorder are compelled to deal with everything since the disorder is incurable in nature. As shared by the participant,

“Sobrang frustrating siya kasi hindi siya compared ng ibang sakit na nakukuha sa gamot, sa therapy, sa technology.” [It’s very frustrating because, unlike with other illnesses, they can be cured by medicines, therapies, or even medical technologies] (Participant 1).

According to the American Senior Communities (2022) study, caregiver strain is highly experienced by caregivers who have a patient with a Major Neurocognitive Disorder because they may develop a set of emotional challenges due to the nature of the disorder. This is relevant to the study’s theme because it was able to establish a link between the impact of experience and its the emotional outcomes. This implies that Filipino family caregivers are indeed frustrated because they have no control over their situation.

Fear of the Disorder’s Severity Phase

The most terrifying situation for family members caring for a patient with terminal illness is when the patient begins its journey on the severity phase of the disorder. Especially in the case of an ajor Neurocognitive Disorder, which frequently leads to a completely dysfunctional state in its patients. As stated by the participant,

“Sa ngayon po kasi malala na po lola ko, talagang kailangan na po niyang assistance sa lahat ng gagawin niya.” [As of now, my grandmother is in her worst condition; she really needs strict assistance in everything she does] (Participant 2).

According to the World Health Organization report (2021) on Major Neurocognitive Disorder, patients who are found to be in their severe stage have an impact on caregivers by shifting their focus from providing care to fostering fear for the worst-case scenario that could happen to their patient. This proves consistency with the theme because family caregivers are frightened of progression as they see changes in their patients' conditions. This also implies that Filipino family caregivers, who typically lack resources, are scared during the disorder's severity phase.

Sense of Helplessness

Aside from the lack of awareness apparent in the amount of literature available in the Philippines, it has also been discovered that family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders experience helplessness due to a lack of support and assistance from both national and local governments. As stated by the participant,

“After learning that this specific condition has no cure really makes me lose hope, until now there are limited to lacking amount of support that is given by the government. Unlike with other countries like the USA, they offer complete assistance not only to the patient but as well as with the caregivers.” (Participant 8).

According to the report published by Word Health Organization (2021), there is a clear lack of recognition and response, including direct governing policies and financial support, in developing countries such as the Philippines, where insurance programs only cover direct medical expenses for hospitalizations. This only implies that the theme of the study is consistent with the literature, as it was able to prove that Filipino family caregivers suffer from a lack of planning for caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Developing Self-Doubt

Dealing with a Major Neurocognitive Disorder is like fighting an invisible foe because no weapon can kill it. Aside from being incurable, it often leaves patients in a critical condition. This is why caregiving assistance is required; however, the patient's outcome is also affected by the caregiver's lack of knowledge about the disorder. As shared by the participant,

“Actually, sa tuwing naiisip ko yung sakit niya is kinakabahan ako kasi may doubt ako kung kakayanin ko ba or hindi lalo wala naman ako masyadong alam sa ganun.” [Actually, whenever I think of his disorder, I feel nervous because I doubt myself if I can endure it or not, specially I don’t have any idea about it] (Participant 3).

In relation to the study of Morais (2022), there is reportedly no global system of universal public healthcare that's capable of offering all of the elements required to address this disorder. As a result, caregivers are solely responsible for managing care and making decisions. However, their lack of knowledge forms self-doubts that impact the caregiving process. This shows consistency with the presented theme since it was able to mention that caregivers who lack knowledge are bound to form self-doubt in taking care of the patient with a Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Presence of Caregiving Fatigue

With a disorder that necessitates caregiving assistance, caregivers are exposed to caregiver strain, in which these are the experiences that test a caregiver's capability and state of health. Given the nature of the disorder, it is entirely possible for caregivers to become

exhausted at some point in their caregiving experience. As shared by the participant,

"I feel like wala ng katapusan to and sobrang depressing niya kasi napapagod na rin ako sa mga nangyayari." [I feel like there's no end to this and it's completely depressing because I feel tired about everything that's happening] (Participant 5).

According to the World Health Organization (2021), caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders are at risk of developing fatigue from their caregiving experience because the disorder has no cure and only requires assistance from a caregiver for the patient to survive. This exemplifies the theme's consistency because it was able to match the outcome of the results, which revealed that caregivers are indeed fatigued as a result of their caregiving experience.

Personal Concern in Caring with Major Neurocognitive Disorder

Presence of the threat that the patient could hurt anybody

A number of different health conditions, drug interactions, or whatever circumstance that makes it harder for someone to process information can all contribute to anxiety and agitation. Individuals with Major Neurocognitive Disorder, on the other hand, are physiologically enduring an extensive impairment of their capacity to interpret new information and input. It is an inevitable outcome of the condition. In addition to the memory loss and mood swings associated with the condition, family caregivers of people suffering from MND may be concerned that their loved ones would become violent or agitated, perhaps causing injury to themselves or others. According to one participant,

"siguro yung idea na pwede siya makasakit unconsciously" (Participant 1) Another participant stated, "Maaaring hindi na talaga siya mag respond sa lahat ng bagay at kinakatakot ko yun kasi pwedeng ako hindi niya ma-recognize bigla niyang masakatan" (Participant 7)

Identifying anxiety in patients' triggers could prove instructive for caregivers. Anxiety can represent a symptom of the condition. According to some studies, anxiety can be a side effect of the brain's transition from normal aging to cognitive impairment. Naturally, it may also occur when individuals with Major Neurocognitive Disorder face traumatic situations connected with aging bodies and brains. Grinberg, (2019)

People with Major Neurocognitive Disorder have brains that are "processing differently and processing more slowly." It's easy for these individuals to feel overwhelmed and overstimulated, and accumulating fears can be triggered just by experiencing feeling uneasy — having been hungry or restless. They will worry over simple things. However, they may be unable to express or address an issue on their own. Drew, (2019) Professionals recommended that family members follow their loved one's routine as closely as necessary. Additionally, playing a person's favorite music and other behavioral methods of distraction.

The Feeling of Uncertainty and Incapability of Providing Care.

Caregiving is a demanding responsibility which can cause physical, mental, and financial strain for caregivers. Family caregivers' experiences far greater rates of physiological complications, stress, anxiety, and burden. The uncertainty about future events may put family members in a difficult position and add to the caregiver's burden. Emotions like guilt, resentment, sadness, and the effort expended as well as the anticipated loss of the relative emerge if they believe to be incapable as caregivers. As stated by one participant,

"lagi na po ako nag ooverthink na baka makalabas po siya ng bahay at hindi na matandaan paano umuwi tapos kasunod na noon yung pag-aalala ko sa kung ano pang mga mas malalang pwede mangyari sa katagalan. Iniiisip ko kung tam aba yung way ko ng pag-aalaga sakanya" (Participant 2) Another Participant stated, "Yung time talaga. Super hirap imanage. Kumbaga hindi namin hawak yung kinabukasan parang ganon. Pati yung kakayahan ko sap ag-aalaga sakanya hindi ko sure kug appropriate pa ba. " (Participant 9) " talagang appektado personal life and time ko. I don't mean it in a bad way ha" (Participant 8) added.

According to Mishel, (1998) the uncertainty concerning conditions as "the inability to understand and to identify the implications of illness-related circumstances and is a cognitive state created when an individual cannot appropriately organize or classify an event due to the lack of adequate cues."

The patient's medical condition, the family's relationship with the patient, and the family's educational level are known to affect the family's perceived level of uncertainty, which leads to anxiety, stress, and a care-giving mindset. Mitchell et al. (2004).

The Lack of Cooperation of the Patient

Being a caregiver for a relative who has a Major Neurocognitive Disorder is difficult and at frequently overwhelming. Many of the challenges of being a caregiver can cause frustration, which is a normal and acceptable response to emotion. There are many unpredictable circumstances you deal with as a dementia caregiver. Normal everyday chores such as dressing, bathing, and eating which causes the problem with the patient's cooperation. One participant stated,

"It is lack of cooperation by the patient that concerns me. Although I want to make her time worthwhile, it still depends to my mother's attitude for certain times which make me a little stressed out. Nakakafrustrate talaga pag mahirap siya pakiusapan" (Participant 10)

According to Branger (2019), in addition to assisting with activities of daily living such as bathing, dressing, and eating, family

caregivers frequently perform medical or nursing chores that are typically handled by nurses. Family caregivers confront common challenges that cause them to feel overwhelmed, apprehensive, and intimidated by their responsibilities.

Caregivers need to guarantee that personal needs are addressed. This will contribute to the treatment of their patients more likely to generate collaboration than dispute. Caregivers who are rushed, irritable, or exasperated frequently set themselves up for very uncooperative conduct from dementia patients, who can become greatly disturbed by such feelings. Alzheimer's Disease Association. (n.d.)

The Lack of Personal Support for the Family Caregiver

Family caregivers play a critical role in providing care and support for their loved ones, often at great personal sacrifice. These caregivers are invaluable assets to our healthcare system as they offer vital services that cannot be substituted by any other means. It is essential to recognize the contributions of family caregivers and establish adequate support systems that address their unique needs needed by their family members with dementia but often struggle on their own with limited support as current systems of support for caregivers are limited. As stated by one participant,

"Lack of resources from the government both local and national" (Participant 3) Another participant stated, "Yung suporta, nakukulangan ako sa pakiramdam na suportado ako" (Participant 5)

According to Mittelman, (2006) on the study of improving the caregiving, caregivers that are inadequate of support are more likely to face challenges and abandon their caregiving tasks. There may be immense advantages for individuals with Major Neurocognitive Disorder, caregivers themselves, the entire healthcare sector, and society as a whole if caregivers have access to better professional consultation and supportive services. Data on the scope of the escalating impact of dementia on nations are provided by the World Health Organization (WHO) which specific reports have examined the prevalence and economic repercussions of the condition at the national level. To have understanding on the population demands such as prevalence and community awareness. A review of current community, social, and health systems and services, including caregiver assistance programs, as well as a gap analysis, should be conducted. (WHO, 2012).

Financial Struggle

The significant hidden unpaid costs endured by caregivers, which are significant, may be overlooked from or understated in estimations of costs. Indirect costs include lost earnings by patients and family caregivers as they leave or reduce job opportunities hours of informal care, and the burden. As stated by one participant,

"Financial matters talaga yung concern ko, sobrang hirap talaga hindi ko makakaila" (Participant 6) "Hindi ko alam kung hanggang saan ko siya kayang maalagaan, what if kung magkulang pera ko, what if kung walang wala na talaga" (Participant 4) added.

According to the Marikina Memory and Aging Project, the Philippines' lack of recognition and inadequate response to Major Neurocognitive Disorder has been studied. Research on epidemiology can raise public awareness of the width of the condition and influence government policy in allocating resources to dementia treatment and prevention, which is critical in areas with limited healthcare resources. These informational factors are crucial as demand for Major Neurocognitive Disorder care is likely to expand as the number of individuals with the condition grows. The entire cost of the condition's care in the Philippines has been projected to be 849.2 million US dollars, with 321.3 million spent on informal care assuming 1.6 hours of ADL care by the caregiver per day. (Agapito et al, 2018). In accordance with the study, as reported by Front Public Health (2021), PhilHealth and other health-care systems, like as SSS, just compensate for hospitalization. Even with government assistance and medical cost reimbursements, Alzheimer's medicines remain prohibitively expensive. The overall financial burden on households is not much impacted by national health insurance. Long-term residential dementia care boosts informal costs over official prices.

Adapting to Situational Changes

One emergent topic centered on the adaptation of Filipino family caregivers to environmental changes in caring for patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders emerged from the clustered meaning. This section discusses five situational adjustments that were developed as a result of data analysis.

Managing Stressor

The respondents emphasized that family caregivers can experience a range of challenges when caring for a loved one with dementia, including financial, social, and emotional stressors. The progressive nature of the disease can lead to increased caregiving demands over time, and the uncertainty of the condition can make planning for the future difficult. Additionally, the physical and emotional toll of caregiving can lead to burnout, depression, and other health problems, making it challenging for caregivers to provide the best possible care for their loved one.

‘‘Alam mo yung galing ka na sa buong araw na pagod sabay pag-uwi is pagod pa rin kasi kailangan mo magalaga ng may sakit. Hindi ka na nakakapagpahinga kasi kailangan mo pa din gawin kasi responsibilidad mo yun.’’ [You know when you come home from the whole day and are tired; you are still tired because you have to take care of someone who is sick. You can't rest anymore because you

still have to do it because it's your responsibility] (Participant 5). Another participant added. "Yung pagod emotionally saka physically. Sa sitwasyon ko magkaakibat talaga siya at sobrang hirap masanay. Yun yung hanggang ngayon pilot kong kontrolin." [He's tired emotionally and physically. In my situation, he's really hard to get used to. That's what I've been trying to control until now.] (Participant 9)

In relation with the reports of American Senior Communities (2022), the greatest caregiver strain is experienced by individuals taking care of a family member with dementia. Family caregiver pressure increases as the condition worsens over time. Since the purpose of caring is to meet the patients' needs, the caregiver's role will obviously need to be altered to do so, regardless of the consequences on their personal lives (Hazzan, et al. 2022). A qualitative approach was employed in the previous study to gather information on the stress felt by family caregivers and the causes of it. The unpredictability of the patient's behavior, coupled with the constant demands of caregiving, can lead to feelings of frustration, exhaustion, and helplessness. Additionally, the gradual decline in the patient's cognitive abilities can be difficult to witness and accept, adding to the caregiver's stress.

There's a Practice of Sacrificing Oneself for the Patient.

Family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients often have to sacrifice their own needs because caring for a loved one with dementia can be a full-time job that requires constant attention and care. The caregiver may have to give up their own social life, hobbies, and career to provide care to their loved one. Additionally, they may have to provide financial support, which can put a strain on their own finances. Finally, the emotional toll of caregiving can be overwhelming, leading the caregiver to prioritize the needs of the patient over their own.

"Yung changes po kasi long time na siya and siguro nagstart po yun sa pag prioritize sa lola ko kaysa sa sarili ko po" [The changes are because he has been around for a long time and maybe that started by prioritizing my grandmother over myself] (Participant 2). Another participant added. "Sacrificing my needs para lang unahin yung needs ng father ko" [Sacrificing my needs just to put my father's needs first] (Participant 3)

According to American Senior Communities (2022) Caregivers frequently find that they have less time for themselves and their other family members. People frequently spend so much time on care tasks that they end up skipping fun pursuits like hobbies or vacations. A family caregiver is typically at a high risk for depression. People frequently devote so much time to caring duties that they are unable to continue their previous social lives. Family caregivers of dementia patients often have to sacrifice their own needs because of the high level of care required by the patient. This can include providing around-the-clock assistance with activities of daily living, such as dressing, bathing, and eating, as well as managing medications and attending medical appointments. The physical and emotional demands of caregiving can leave little time for the caregiver to tend to their own needs, leading to stress, fatigue, and a decline in their own health. Furthermore, the financial burden of caregiving can also lead to a sacrifice of the caregiver's personal needs, as they may need to reduce their working hours or give up their job entirely to provide care.

Difficulties in the Daily Routine.

It is evident in the respondents that they had a hard time in dealing with patients in their everyday life. Family caregivers of dementia patients face numerous struggles, including the physical and emotional demands of providing care, the unpredictable behavior of the patient, and the gradual decline in the patient's cognitive abilities. This can lead to feelings of frustration, exhaustion, and helplessness, as well as a decline in the caregiver's own health and well-being. Caregivers may also face financial burdens, as they may need to reduce their working hours or give up their job entirely to provide care. The lack of support and resources for caregivers can exacerbate these struggles, making it difficult for them to manage the stressors of caregiving and maintain their own well-being.

"yung daily routine talaga since ito yung nabago ng buong buo. kahit mga simpleng gawaing bahay nahihirapan na siyang gawin kaya walang ibang gagawa kundi ako na lang " ["It's really the daily routine since it's completely changed. Even simple household chores are difficult for him to do, so no one else will do it but me.] (Participant 7) Another participant added. "kapag umuwi ako dati siya sumasalubong sakin tapos may naka ready ng pagkain" [When I come home, he used to meet me and have food ready] (Participant 5)

There is growing evidence that frequently reported difficulties faced by family caregivers of individuals with late-stage dementia include a lack of preparation for end-of-life discussions, regret and stress associated with their loved one's institutionalization, lack of familiarity with death in general and death brought on by developing dementia, a limited comprehension of the natural occurrence of late-stage dementia, and a lack of knowledge with establishing goals and measures (Nunns, 2015). The lack of support and resources for caregivers can also exacerbate their stress levels and make it difficult for them to manage the daily challenges of caregiving. Overall, the role of a family caregiver for a dementia patient can be incredibly challenging and requires a significant amount of dedication and sacrifice.

Lining up for Possible Source of Assistance.

Family caregivers of dementia patients can have a hard time looking for assistance in caring for their loved ones due to several factors. One factor is the stigma surrounding dementia, which can make it difficult for caregivers to seek help or talk about their experiences. Another factor is the lack of available resources and support systems, including respite care, home health aides, and support groups. Furthermore, navigating the healthcare system and understanding insurance coverage can be challenging and time-consuming. Finally,

the cost of care and the financial burden of caregiving can limit access to services for some caregivers. All of these factors can make it difficult for family caregivers to find the assistance they need to provide the best possible care for their loved ones with dementia.

"Yung paghahanap ng resources, kasi hindi talaga sapat yung trabaho ko kaya minsan napunta kami sa city hall. Yung pakiramdam na hopeless ka na kasi hindi mo na alam kung kanino ka pa hihinge ng tulong" [The search for resources, because my work is not really enough, so sometimes we went to the city hall. The feeling that you are hopeless because you don't know who else to ask for help] (Participant 6) Another participant added. "We had difficulty in the adverse changes on the healthcare planning." (Participant 10)

In the Canadian study by Branger (2019), they supplied documents that were used to perform an analysis to fully grasp the phenomena of positive features of caregiving. Before undertaking a quantitative and qualitative inquiry with a sample of caregivers of persons living with dementia, they conduct a thorough search, synthesis, and integration of studies on the advantageous elements of caregiving. In addition to that, most family caregivers are unpaid, which can cause them to experience some financial burden, particularly if providing care requires them to leave a paying career. The financial impact on the family caregiver increases with the length of time they have been giving care (American Senior Communities, 2022). The cost of long-term care can be significant, and some families may not have adequate resources to cover the expenses. All of these factors can make it difficult for family caregivers to manage the financial aspects of caregiving, adding to the already significant emotional and physical demands of caring for a loved one with Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Incapability of the Patient to Do Task

Based on the experience of the respondent, Major Neurocognitive Disorders patients may struggle to perform tasks that were once routine or simple for them due to the progressive deterioration of cognitive function and memory loss associated with the disease. As the disease progresses, the ability to process information, make decisions, and perform daily activities can become increasingly challenging for the patient. However, depending on the stage of the disease and the specific tasks involved, some dementia patients may still be able to perform certain activities or tasks as a normal person would. It is important to note that the abilities of each dementia patient can vary widely, and it is essential to provide individualized support and care to address their specific needs and abilities.

"Yung may makasama sa bahay na may dementia, parang nag-aalaga ka kasi ng bata kapag sila kasama mo" [When you live with someone with dementia, it's like you're taking care of a child when they're with you] (Participant 4) Another participant added. "Maaaring hindi na talaga siya mag respond sa lahat ng bagay at kinakatakot ko yun kasi pwedeng ako hindi niya ma-recognize bigla niyang masaktan. Nakakamiss din talaga yung dati na makita ko siyang malakas. Yung mga panahon na nagagawa nya pa yung mga bagay na dati nyang ginagawa para sa pamilya namin" [He might not really respond to everything and I'm afraid of that because he might not recognize me and suddenly get hurt. I also really miss the time when I used to see him strong. The times when he was still able to do the things that he used to do it for our family] (Participant 7)

According to World Health Organization (2021), at the last stage of neurocognitive disorder caregiver responsibilities include personal care, transportation, mobility and protection, and cleaning. The majority of caregiver's experience role strain at this point as a result of exhaustion and a low quality of life for the reason of incapability of the patient to do the things they used to do when they are not yet diagnosed with this kind of disorder. Taking care of Major Neurocognitive Disorders patients can be incredibly challenging due to the progressive deterioration of their cognitive abilities and the impact this has on their daily functioning. Caregivers may need to provide around-the-clock assistance with tasks such as bathing, dressing, and eating, as well as managing medications and attending medical appointments.

Situational Realization of the Existence of Anticipatory Grief

The clustered meaning formed single emergent themes that revolve around the existence of anticipatory grief of Filipino Family caregiver of Major Neurocognitive patients. Four situational realization of the existence of anticipatory grief have been developed as a result of data analysis and are discussed in this section.

Inability to Feel the Presence of the Patient even when Seen Physically

It is evident in the experience of respondents that the inability to feel the presence of a dementia patient, even when seen physically, can be due to several factors. Dementia patients may experience a progressive deterioration of cognitive abilities, resulting in disconnection from their surroundings. Physical changes, such as lack of eye contact and slurred speech, can also impact emotional connection. Additionally, the emotional toll of caregiving and constant demands can make it difficult for caregivers to focus on the patient's emotional needs. Furthermore, caregivers may experience their psychological factors that impact their ability to connect emotionally. Ultimately, the inability to feel the presence of a dementia patient can lead to feelings of isolation and confusion for both the patient and the caregiver.

"Parang kahit nakikita ko po siya, parang wala na rin kasi hindi na po tulad ng dati na nakakausap ko pa. Ngayon na nadiagnosed sya na meron sakit parang lahat ng bagay nag bago na sa kanya hindi ko na sya nakakausap kagaya ng dati hindi na naming nagagawa yung mga bagay na ginagawa naming dati" [It's like even though I can see him, it's like he's gone because it's not like before that I can talk to him. Now that he was diagnosed with a disease, it seems like everything has changed with him, I can't talk to him like before, we can't do the things we used to do] (Participant 2). Another participant added. "kahit nandyan sya para wala na. may mga oras na

kailangan itakbo sa ospital kasi may other na sakit pa, sobrang nakakapanghina"[Even though he's there so he's gone. There are times when I have to run to the hospital because I have another illness, it's very debilitating] (Participant 5)

Dementia-related losses, often known as caregiver grieving, are pre-death grief for the caregiver, according to Cheever (2015). The emotional responses to the losses connected to caregiving, such as sadness, burden, and loneliness, are referred to as this sort of mourning. Grief experienced by the caregiver can have a significant impact on their mood, health, social life, and performance at work and at home. Their lives become unpredictable and disorganized after losing a caretaker. The personalities, thoughts, and capacities of dementia sufferers can change dramatically. Patients occasionally show up in remarkably contradictory situations at once, such as being both "here" and "gone" or both "alive" and "dead." Caregivers also experience a sense of identity loss, going from being an adult kid to almost a parental figure or from being a spouse to an unidentified stranger. Dementia sufferers appear physically unaltered but are psychologically "lost." The caregiver finds it difficult to understand and accept these inconsistencies.

Major Neurocognitive Disorder Transcends the Occurrence of "Lose."

Major Neurocognitive Disorder, formerly known as dementia, is a condition that goes beyond the simple notion of "losing" one's cognitive abilities. This disorder represents a significant decline in cognitive function that impacts an individual's ability to perform everyday activities. The loss of cognitive function affects various domains of a person's life, including memory, language, attention, perception, and problem-solving abilities. This decline can result in significant changes in a person's personality, behavior, and emotions. It is important to recognize that Major Neurocognitive Disorder is a complex condition that requires a comprehensive approach to care and support, as it can have a profound impact on an individual's quality of life and those around them.

"humihingi ako ng tulong at nagmamakaawa ako, parang yung feeling ko is life and death situation na yung condition, sobrang kaba, takot, at pigil hininga talaga. Hindi ko maiwasan magisip nab aka anytime babawian na sya ng buhay kaya palagi ako nangangamba." [I'm asking for help and I'm begging, it's like I feel like the condition is a life and death situation, I'm really nervous, afraid, and holding my breath. I can't help but think that he's going to die anytime, so I'm always worried.] (Participant 6) Another participant added. "Salitang dementia pa lang ang unang pumapasok na sa isip ko is pagkawala" [The word dementia is the first thing that comes to my mind is loss] (Participant 4)

The patient's condition worsens as the illness does. Several studies have already looked at how caregiving affects the quality of life of the caregivers. Also, some writers have included the idea of anticipatory mourning for family caregivers who worry about a loved one's impending death (Lewis, 2014). Dementia caregivers may fear the death of the patient for several reasons. They may have developed a strong emotional bond with the patient, making the thought of losing them particularly difficult to bear. Caring for a person with dementia can be an extremely demanding and stressful task, and the death of the patient can mean the end of this challenging journey. The caregiver may worry about their own future, especially if the patient was the primary source of emotional, financial, or social support. Finally, caregivers may also experience feelings of guilt or regret, especially if they feel that they could have done more to improve the patient's quality of life. Ultimately, the fear of the death of a dementia patient is a complex and emotional experience that can have a significant impact on the caregiver's mental health and well-being.

Situation that Triggered the Participant to Think they are Grieving.

Based on the situations that the respondent experience, family caregivers of individuals with dementia often experience anticipatory grief, which is the process of grieving before a loss has actually occurred. This is because dementia is a chronic and progressive illness, and caregivers may experience a sense of loss as they witness their loved one's cognitive abilities and personality change over time. Anticipatory grief can take many forms, including feelings of sadness, anxiety, guilt, anger, and frustration. Caregivers may also experience a sense of helplessness and hopelessness as they watch their loved one's condition deteriorate. Additionally, caregivers may grieve for the loss of their relationship with the person they once knew, as the person with dementia may no longer be able to engage in activities or conversations they once enjoyed.

"One morning, nagpanic ako kasi hindi ko siya mahanap sa bahay turns out sinama pala siya pumasal ng kapatid ko tas after that, talagang umiyak ako. Hindi ko maiwasan magisip na baka may mangyare na masama sa kanya. Kaya ganun yung reaction ko kapag nawawala siya sa paningin ko" [One morning, I panicked because I couldn't find him at home. It turns out that my brother went with him for a walk. After that, I really cried. I couldn't help but think that something bad might happen to him. That's the way I react when he goes missing out of my sight] (Participant 8)

In related to that according to the study Park, J. & Galvin, J. (2021) found that pre-loss grieving is linked to lower psychological well-being. Caregiver stress refers to psychological and emotional reactions to the difficulties of providing care, which is a direct result of their sense of solitude in their duty. This stress is said to have an inverse proportion to one's well-being. A substantial impact undoubtedly is seen on a carer's psychological health after having provided attention to family members with Major Neurocognitive Disorders.

True enough, when families or family members take less direct participation in the care—as seen in placing patients in care homes—of patients, losses become much more significant. It seems apparent, per the study that increased burden predicted pre-loss grief (Park & Galvin, 2021).

The Respondent Felt in a Rush of Providing Everything before it's Too late.

Family caregivers of individuals with dementia may feel like they are running out of time for several reasons. One of the primary reasons is that dementia is a progressive and degenerative disease, which means that the symptoms and challenges associated with the disease typically worsen over time. As a result, caregivers may feel like they need to make the most of the time they have with their loved one before their condition deteriorates further. In addition, caring for someone with dementia can be a demanding and time-consuming responsibility. Caregivers may feel like they are constantly on call and may struggle to balance their caregiving duties with other responsibilities, such as work, family, and personal time. This can create a sense of urgency and pressure to get everything done before time runs out.

"Siguro yung thought na gawin mo na lahat para makapagpaalam ng maayos, before pa mawala. Ayaw ko na mangare na sa huli ako magsisi kasi wala na siya" [Maybe the thought is that you should do everything to say goodbye properly, before it's gone. I don't want to worry that in the end I'll regret it because he's gone] (Participant 5). Another participant added. "kinakausap ko na siya in a way na parang nagpapaalam. I am assuring him na kahit ano man ang mangyari ay nasa maayos ng kalagayan kami" [I have been talking to him in a way as if to say goodbye. I am assuring him that no matter what happens, we will be fine] (Participant 3)

In related to the study of Lewis (2014) The possibility of being forgotten by a loved one is consistently implied when the word "dementia" is used. Participants in this study agree that there is a yearning for companionship because, despite being physically present with the patient, the bond of the relationship has been blocked due to the symptoms of severe dementia. Patients in the later stages of dementia have a natural tendency to completely lose their memories. Since it is also thought that family caregivers become furious at the idea that the illness will prevent them from spending the rest of their lives with the patient, they go through the process of saying a long goodbye and grieving for the future that has been stolen from them and their patient during this stage. Overall, the combination of the progressive nature of dementia, the demands of caregiving, and the uncertainty of the future can contribute to a sense of running out of time for family caregivers of individuals with dementia. It is important for caregivers to prioritize self-care and seek support to manage the stress and challenges of caregiving.

Coping Strategies of Filipino Family Caregivers

The clustered meanings formed a single emergent theme that revolves around Filipino family caregivers' coping strategies when dealing with emotional crises caused by the patient's apparent memory loss. Six coping strategies have been developed as a result of the data analysis and are discussed in this section.

Caregiving

The respondents emphasized that the simplest and easiest form of coping in their situation with the patient is to provide care. Despite the fact that it may sound repetitive, caregiving is frequently the coping strategy chosen by caregivers because it gives them comfort and peace to know that no matter what happens to the patient, at least they were able to help and serve them by providing care. Two of the participants stated,

"Sa totoo lang, dumating man sa punto na miski ako hindi na niya maalala, iisipin ko na lang na laman pa rin ako ng puso niya dahil kahit papaano nakita naman niya kung paano ko siya pagsilbihan kahit noon pa man na wala pa siyang sakit at hanggang sa ma-diagnose siya. Magmula umpisa hanggang dulo, ako ang nag-aalaga kaya kahit masakit, iniisip ko na lang talaga na wala naman ng tutumbas sa pag-aalaga ko." [To be honest, if the patient ever reaches the point where he is unable to recognize me, I will just think that I'm still in his heart due to the fact that he observed my care for him before the diagnosis and throughout the time leading up to it. I have been caring for him from the beginning until the present. Despite how much it hurts, I'll just continue to believe that providing care is incomparable and immeasurable] (Participant 1). Another participant added, "Kaya kahit nakakalimot na siya, na-cocomfort ako sa idea na napagsilbihan ko pa rin siya." [Even though he has memory loss, I'm still comforted by the idea that I was able to take care of him] (Participant 4).

In relation with the study conducted by Branger (2019), the sense of fulfillment that comes from the experience is one of the positive aspects of caregiving since it allows the caregivers to think of the silver lining of their situation with the patient. Furthermore, caregiving experience shapes caregivers' adaptive coping styles, leading them to evaluate and assess their situation and devise solutions (J Caring Sci, 2018). Given that the Filipino family caregivers view "caregiving" as a positive aspect of their experience with the patient, this is consistent with the study's generated theme, which identifies caregiving as one of the fundamental forms of coping strategies due to the obtained sense of fulfillment of the Filipino family caregivers.

Quality Time with the Patient

Spending the remaining time with a patient who has a terminal illness is the typical response of family caregivers. Some family caregivers sacrifice their careers and other obligations during this time in order to spend as much time as possible developing a bond with the patient. As mentioned by the respondent,

"Hinding hindi po namin siya susukuan at papabayaang, hanggang ngayon sinusubukan po namin gawin yung mga paborito niyang gawin dati pero this time with proper guidance na po talaga naming. As much as possible mas maraming time na po ang binibigay sa

kanya.” [We will never give up on him or neglect him; instead, we are still working to engage him in some of his previous favorite hobbies while providing as much time as we can] (Participant 2).

The end-of-life caregiving for patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders involves five stages, according to Lewis (2014). The second stage relates to the reactions of the caregivers when they learn that their loved one has a limited lifespan. As a result, their initial response is to spend as much time as they can with that person and make memories that they will treasure forever. This demonstrates how strongly the study's developed theme is supported by the literature, and this implies the fact that Filipino family caregivers value quality time spent with patients as a coping strategy for their situation.

Recollection of the Past

People were brought together by their shared memories, which led them to develop a bond with one another. Once these memories are lost, a sense of absence and emptiness is felt. The moment the patient exhibits memory loss, caregivers who have Major Neurocognitive Disorders experience anxiety. As a means to cope with this scenario, the caregivers recollect past memories. As shared by the participant,

“I always show him pictures, lagi ko siyang binubuklatan ng album namin tapos ikukwento ko sa kanya kung ano yung mga nangyari behind that picture, nagiging way ko na rin yun para makaramdam ng connection sa kanya kahit hindi na nagresponse ng maayos.” [I always show him pictures, I tend to open the photo album then tell all the stories behind every picture. It is my way to feel connected with him even though he doesn't respond anymore the way he used to be] (Participant 3).

According to the findings of Hazzan et al. (2022), family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders see themselves as a source of support for the patient. This includes the adjustments that were made in order for the patient's needs to be met. It entails a desire to be involved in the patient's battle with the disorder, regardless of how difficult it is. Caregivers gain the willingness to do what is best for the patient. This literature displays a connection with the study's produced theme because it was able to mention that caregivers are willing to go to any length to provide care for the patient. This can be seen in the participant's case wherein recollection of memories was one of the Filipino family caregiver's coping strategies once the patient's memory loss worsened.

Firmness in Spiritual Reliance

People's typical reaction to uncontrollable or unforeseen situations is to hold on to their faith and reach out to their supreme being through prayers. Most caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders acknowledge this because, in the face of uncertainty, it is their faith that keeps them going. As stated by the two of the participants,

“Through praying, talagang nilelet go ko na lahat ng worries at burdens ko kay Lord kasi sa situation naman namin wala naman kasiguraduhan lalo na if wala namang lunas sa sakit niya. Sobrang hirap at nakakapagod kaya naman talagang kay Lord na lang ako nakapit.” [Through praying, I let go of all of my worries and burdens to the Lord. Since my situation is uncertain as this illness is incurable, it's very hard and tiring for me. That's why I hold on to my Lord] (Participant 5). “Kumakapit na lang talaga ako ngayon kay Lord at sa pamilya ko na bigyan ako ng lakas para kayanin lahat kasi hindi ko na rin alam.” [I depend now to the Lord and to my family to give me strength in order to endure everything because I don't really know] (Participant 7).

In consistency with the literature authored by Cruz & Dominguez (2020), the Philippines adheres to the beliefs of Christians and majority of the Filipino families are Roman Catholic. It is very evident that religion and faith are significant coping strategies in relation to Major Neurocognitive Disorder care. This would mean that it is already given in the blood line of many Filipinos, regardless of whether they are a caregiver or not, to be firm on their spiritual principles in times of uncertainty.

Conversation with Others

The theory of ambiguous loss by Pauline Boss (2002), explains the caregiver's situation of developing stressors due to the sudden exposure to a scenario where an attachment between two close people is unfelt because of the impact of Major Neurocognitive Disorders. This often triggers the caregivers to suffer from loneliness and helplessness since the person they used to be close with may be physically present but mentally absent. As mentioned by the participant,

“I talk my worries out to other people. Parang way of venting ba or release ng worries kasi ang bigat sa kalooban kapag binibitbit ko lang.” [I talk my worries out to other people. It is my way of venting or releasing of worries because it feels to heavy if I keep on hiding it to myself] (Participant 8).

From the study of Nunns (2015), the literature mentions that family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders were discovered to be struggling with the feeling of overload. This means that family caregivers also reach their limit, and when it happens, the initial response will be to talk with other people as a means to express one's feelings about their situation. This completely reveals consistency with the theme of the study as it was able to match the literature's provided information.

The Practice of Empathizing

The fine line between sympathy and empathy is that sympathy simply refers to shared feelings, whereas empathy is the desire to put oneself in the shoes of others who are suffering from a situation and understand them through that lens. Some of the patients don't like

to be pitied, and they try to avoid situations where they put other people through hardship. When it comes to family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders, they empathize rather than sympathize in order to comprehend the patient's world. As shared by the participant,

“I’d like to think she is also still doing her best to see the world through her eyes and trying to respond to the “feeling” behind the behavior” (Participant 10).

In relation with the study of United Kingdom Alzheimer’s Society (2015), it was stated that without the assistance and support of family caregivers, the official care system for Major Neurocognitive Disorders would fail. This suggests that the role of the family caregiver in the patient's condition is to determine the most appropriate lens through which to view the patient's situations. This is consistent with the theme because it stresses how vital it is to grasp the patient's perspective in order to comprehend the changes taking place in their lives.

Anticipatory Grief among Filipino Family Caregivers

The data analysis for the study yielded seven formulated meanings, which were consolidated into one emergent theme that predominantly highlights the role of anticipatory grief among Filipino family caregivers in preparing for the patient's life course. In this section, the presence of anticipatory grief and its impact on Filipino family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders were thoroughly discussed with reference to the literature.

A Chance to Fill the Gaps

People, regardless of their roles, experience fear after learning that a loved one has an incurable and terminal disease; this fear signifies the anticipatory grief that was created when the patient's condition was revealed. This places additional pressure on family members to reconsider their approach or the way the patient is being treated. As a result, they were able to determine what was lacking and construct a solution to address it. As shared by the participant,

“Now, na napapansin kong malala na, mas lalo ko na ginagawa yung mga gusto ko gawin for her. I can buy more time para mabigay yung mga gusto niya, and maparanas yung mga hindi pa niya naeexperience. Somehow, iniisip ko na mawala man siya, at least nagawa ko lahat.” [Now, I’ve noticed that her condition worsened, I’m doing the things I like to do for her. I can buy more time in order to give her what she wants and make her experience the things she hasn’t yet experienced. Somehow, I’m thinking that even after she passed away, at least I was able to do everything] (Participant 1).

According to the study of Park & Galvin (2021), the decision-making process for the patient's treatment plans frequently begins when caregivers notice significant changes in their patients. This can happen even before the patient actually passes away. This demonstrates consistency with the theme that was created because it was capable of elucidating how fear on the part of the caregiver frequently results in the choice to fill in the gaps as a way to make up for what is missing.

A Time to be Expressive

When it comes to their affection for each other, some family relationships are not always expressive and obvious. The vast majority of family members prefer to express their love language through service. Meanwhile, others prefer to express themselves through written letters. It is uncommon to see family members who are expressive or vocal about their feelings for one another. However, as part of anticipatory grief, it encourages family members to express their feelings for the patient. According to the participant,

“Hmm.. siguro po yung nasasabi ko na po at napapakita kung gaano po ako ka-thankful sa kanya sa lahat ng nagawa niya po for me.” [Hmm, I can say now and show of how thankful I am for everything that he did to me] (Participant 3).

Cheung et al. (2018) found that anticipatory grief puts family caregivers in a state of uncertainty, which encourages them to be expressive towards the patient. Aside from providing care, they are also encouraged to express their feelings about the patient. This demonstrates the theme's reliability by proving that being expressive is part of the impact and influence of anticipatory grief among Filipino family caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Filipino Family Caregiver’s Preparations for the Patient

With the presence of uncertainty and a lack of knowledge on the nature of the disorder due to its quality of being incurable and fatal, caregivers are often left in a situation where they plan ahead for the patient. These plans revolve around caregiving routines, processes, and practices. As shared by the participant,

“Yung grieving or pagpapaalam napapa-process agad siya ng maaga, parang nagkakaroon ng linaw sa isipan ko kung ano yung mga dapat gawin habang nandyan pa siya. Nagkakaroon ako ng idea sa mga activities na pwedeng makatulong sa kanya.” [It makes the grieving process begin earlier than expected; it’s like there’s an enlightenment in my mind about the things that we can do while he’s still here. I gain ideas about the activities that can help him] (Participant 4).

According to the study of González et al. (2021), claims that anticipatory grief helps caregivers be ready for the decline in cognitive, behavioral, and functional abilities that the disease will bring. As a result, caregivers prepare a list of possible approaches in terms of

their caregiving setup. This reveals consistency with the study's supplied theme because it exemplifies that, no matter the nation or ethnicity of the people, caregivers of patients with Major Neurocognitive Disorders share a common experience of the impact the disorder has on their daily lives.

Protection from Guilt

People who have lost a loved one may experience guilt as a result of their shortcomings, flaws, and treatment of the deceased. This guilt is the emotional state that "I could have done that" but couldn't because the person has already died. Anticipatory grief reduces the likelihood of family members developing guilt because it allows for earlier planning, decision-making, and action. According to the participant,

"Inaalis niya ako sa possibility na magsisi kasi what if kung ibang sakit yun and mas mabilis magprogress, tapos tuloy tuloy lang yung gawain ko na gumala, etc. edi mas mataas yung chance na magkaroon talaga ako ng guilt. Pero dahil sa pakiramdam na ito, natutunan ko agad sumabay sa agos at magbago para sa kanya." [It keeps me away from the possibility of feeling guilty because, if it's another illness that is much more progressive, then I continue with my hobbies, etc. It's a higher chance that I may have a sense of guilt. However, due to this feeling, I learned to move with the flow and change for the patient] (Participant 5).

In relation with the study of Huskin (2022), anticipatory grief can elicit a range of difficult emotions, including anger and resentment, guilt, grief, anxiety, and worry about how they will handle the additional responsibilities of caregiving. This indicates a connection to the theme by identifying guilt as part of the anticipatory grief experience. This implies that the presence of pre-loss grief lowers the possibility of developing a sense of guilt in Filipino family caregivers.

Acceptance of the Uncertainty of Death

Human lifespans always end in death, and nothing or no one can stop that from happening; even science can't stop it from happening, but it can reduce the likelihood of it happening sooner than expected by inventing medications and medical technologies. Nonetheless, death is the final stage of life. Caregivers experiencing anticipatory grief face the fear of death as a result of their patient's condition. As shared by the participant,

"Pre-loss grieving helps me to accept that death is inevitable. Talagang kapag oras na ay oras na talaga. Sobrang uncertain kasi ng mga bagay sa ganitong sakit kaya dapat laging prepared." [Pre-loss grieving helps me to accept that death is inevitable. It's just that if it's the person's time, then it's his time. There's so much uncertainty with this kind of disorder, that it's important to be prepared] (Participant 6).

According to Davies et al. (2014), the caregiver's care may progress from the encounter stage, in which they accept the diagnosis and their new role, to the enduring stage, in which the intensity of care increases, to the exit stage, in which they face the patient's death. This reveals consistency with the discussed theme, as it was able to make an emphasis on the presence of death as something that caregivers encounter and have to deal with. With anticipatory grief, the caregivers were able to process the sense of grief even before death occurred.

Acceptance of the Uncertainty of Death

Major Neurocognitive Disorder differs from other terminal illnesses in that it does not have a cure and necessitates extensive caregiving assistance from those who can support the patient. It is also unique in its nature because, in addition to memory loss, the patient also experiences other symptoms caused by other illnesses. For example, in Parkinson's disease, along with the Major Neurocognitive Disorder, the patient also suffers from the impact of the disease, leaving the caregiver to adjust and be knowledgeable about the patient's reality. According to the participant,

"Naiintroduce na agad yung mga worst case scenario and situations. Hindi siya biglaan na mawawala agad kasi nagkakaroon ako ng time para maging mas maalam pa sa sakit niya at kung ano yung mga nangyayari sa mga may sakit na katulad niya." [It introduced the worst-case scenario and situation at the outset. It's not like the other illness, where he'll be gone too soon. That being said, I allocate time to learning about the disorder and its effects on those who suffer from it.] (Participant 7).

It was stated in the report of Webster (2021), a lack of knowledge about a Major Neurocognitive Disorder diagnosis has a significant impact on the quality of care as well as the safety of the patient and their caregiver. This illustrates theme consistency, as the caregivers expose themselves to the patient's reality by being knowledgeable about the disorder as well as the patient's life course. This only implies that caregivers of patients with this disorder are eager to learn about the illness's reality.

A Moment of Life to be Appreciative

Being placed in an uncertain situation with the awareness of impending loss causes caregivers to be grateful for the remaining opportunities, such as the time and chance to be with the patient. Anticipatory grief teaches caregivers to make the most of every experience while there is still time because the patient's condition will worsen, and once that happens, the situation will be unpleasant for everyone. As shared by the participant,

"But I guess it helped in a way that it made me more appreciative of the time we have left to enjoy together because I know that sooner

or later she will be gone and I won't be able to bring back the past, all I have to do is to accept her death.” (Participant 10).

According to Lewis (2014)'s research, the fifth stage of caregiving is to find joy in the experience; this refers to caregivers viewing caregiving as a form of love rather than a response to the patient's needs. Caregivers learn to appreciate the time and the bond that exists with the patient in order to seize the moment. This only proves the theme's consistency because it was able to discuss the caregiver's process of becoming appreciative as a result of the patient's life course with the disorder.

Conclusions

The sense of affection is a significant factor that drives Filipino family caregivers to provide care for their loved ones with Major Neurocognitive Disorder. In Filipino culture, the family bond is highly valued, and the concept of "pagmamahal" or unconditional love is deeply ingrained. The affection and emotional attachment that family caregivers have for their loved ones with dementia can drive them to provide care despite the challenges and hardships that come with caregiving. This sense of duty and love can motivate caregivers to provide emotional, physical, and financial support to ensure their loved ones receive the best possible care. Ultimately, the sense of affection and the importance of familial responsibility in Filipino culture can be powerful motivators for family caregivers of dementia patients.

Filipino family caregivers provide care to dementia patients for various reasons, including cultural values, familial obligations, and financial constraints. In Filipino culture, taking care of elders is considered a moral obligation, and the concept of "utang na loob" (debt of gratitude) but in this study it's proved that caring for elderly relative with Major Neurocognitive Disorder is not ingrained by debt of gratitude. Additionally, many Filipino families do not have access to affordable or adequate healthcare services, leading them to rely on family members to provide care for their loved ones with dementia. Furthermore, due to economic pressures, many Filipino caregivers view caregiving as a way to earn a living and support their families. Thus, Filipino family caregivers provide care to dementia patients out of a sense of duty, love, and necessity.

Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients may display a lack of knowledge about Major Neurocognitive Disorder due to a variety of factors. Firstly, there is a general lack of awareness and understanding about dementia and its associated symptoms and behaviors, which can lead to misconceptions and stigmatization. Additionally, access to information and education about dementia is limited in many parts of the Philippines, particularly in rural areas. The healthcare system in the country also faces numerous challenges, such as inadequate resources and limited healthcare personnel, which can hinder the dissemination of information and knowledge about dementia. As a result, family caregivers may lack the necessary information and skills to provide optimal care for their loved ones with dementia.

Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive patients suffer from strains due to the physical, emotional, and financial burdens of caregiving. The demanding nature of caregiving, including helping with daily activities, managing medications, and dealing with challenging behaviours, can lead to physical exhaustion and health problems. The emotional strain of watching their loved one's mental decline and dealing with behavioural issues can cause depression, anxiety, and other mental health problems. These challenges can lead to burnout, social isolation, and a decreased quality of life for both the caregiver and the person with dementia.

Anticipatory grief is a common experience for Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients due to several reasons. First, caregivers often witness the gradual decline of their loved one's cognitive and functional abilities, leading to a sense of loss and grief over time. Additionally, caregiving can be emotionally taxing and physically demanding, causing caregivers to experience burnout and feelings of sadness and frustration. Overall, the emotional toll of caregiving and the gradual loss of their loved one's abilities can lead Filipino family caregivers to experience anticipatory grief as they navigate the challenges of caring for someone with Major Neurocognitive Disorder.

Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients experience a sense of loss and sadness as they witness the decline of their loved one's personality, memory, and independence. Caregivers often feel overwhelmed with the responsibilities of caregiving and the uncertainty of what the future may hold, leading to feelings of anxiety, stress, and despair. The process of anticipatory grief can also result in caregivers feeling disconnected from their social support networks, increasing their sense of isolation and loneliness. As a result, Filipino family caregivers of dementia patients may require support and interventions to manage their anticipatory grief and maintain their mental health and wellbeing.

Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients adapt to the situation by relying on their cultural values, social support networks, and personal strengths. They often draw upon their sense of duty and obligation to care for their loved ones, finding meaning and purpose in their caregiving roles. Caregivers may also seek support from their families, friends, and communities, who provide emotional and practical assistance. Additionally, caregivers may utilize coping strategies such as seeking respite care, engaging in self-care activities, and finding ways to maintain a positive attitude. Despite the challenges, Filipino family caregivers often display resilience and adaptability, finding ways to cope with the situation and maintain a sense of hope and positivity.

Filipino family caregivers of dementia patients cope with anticipatory grief by utilizing a range of strategies, including seeking support from family and friends, engaging in self-care activities, and finding ways to maintain a positive outlook. They may also rely on their faith and spiritual practices, which are integral parts of Filipino culture. Additionally, they participate in support groups, which provide

opportunities to connect with others who are going through similar experiences. Filipino family caregivers of dementia patients may also find comfort in activities that promote relaxation and reduce stress, such as exercise, meditation, or hobbies. Ultimately, coping with anticipatory grief requires a multifaceted approach that considers the caregiver's cultural background, personal strengths, and individual needs.

Caregiving for a loved one with dementia can lead to changes in family dynamics, with the caregiver assuming a more dominant role in decision-making and daily care. This can lead to a loss of independence and autonomy for both the caregiver and care recipient, further contributing to anticipatory grief. The emotional toll of caregiving, combined with the gradual loss of their loved one's abilities and changes in family dynamics, can create a sense of anticipatory grief for Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive Disorder patients. It is important for caregivers to acknowledge and address these feelings and seek support to manage their emotional wellbeing while providing care.

Anticipatory grief is a common experience for Filipino family caregivers of Major Neurocognitive patients. As they witness the gradual decline of their loved one's cognitive and functional abilities, caregivers may experience a range of emotions, including sadness, guilt, anger, and anxiety. They may feel a sense of loss and mourning for the person their loved one once was, as well as for the future that they had envisioned. Caregivers may also experience anticipatory grief for their own losses, such as the loss of their own identity, freedom, and independence. However, many Filipino family caregivers find ways to cope with anticipatory grief through social support, cultural values, and personal resilience.

Recommendation

There must be accessible essential information materials needed to understand the nature of Major Neurocognitive Disorder, practice self-management and psycho-educational support interventions designed to increase knowledge, skills and ultimately resilience to handle anticipatory grieving provided as it is crucial to family caregivers timely and accurate knowledge as the condition of the relative progress.

It is recommended that national policymakers undertake a thorough assessment of current legislation on financial support for family caregivers and outpatients, intending to enhance its efficacy in reducing their respective financial burden.

The promotion of care services, including peer and community support groups, should be encouraged on a large scale to provide emotional and social assistance that empowers family caregivers to more effectively navigate the difficulties inherent in their responsibilities

Family caregivers should also be willing to accept formal and informal help from intermittent care centers or nursing homes, without feeling embarrassed or overwhelmed. Trust should be established with well-equipped partnership services to promote effective formal care positively as achieving a balance between the demands of providing care and addressing one's personal needs is vital in caregiving.

The proponents of this study strongly suggest future researchers on this topic present their paper to the Alzheimer's Disease Association of the Philippines (ADAP) as a means of providing current and updated information on the study's participants. Engagement in the said organization's webinars, conferences, and research affairs will benefit the study's target audience as well as achieve its objectives.

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